

DEPLOYTOUR
European Tourism Data Space

Call for proposals	DIGITAL-2023-CLOUD-DATA-AI-05	Type of action	DIGITAL-SIMPLE
Grant Agreement No.	101173388	Start date	1 October 2024
Project duration	36 months	End date	30 September 2027

Contact: projects@anysolution.eu

Website: www.deploytour.eu

Project consortium – Coordinator: ANYSOLUTION			
POLITECNICO DI MILANO	BEN – POLIMI	NTT DATA SPAIN	BEN - NTTDES
AMADEUS DATA PROCESSING GmbH	BEN - ADP	AMADEUS GERMANY GmbH	AE - AMADEUS GERMANY
EONA-X	BEN – EONA-X	ITALIAN MINISTRY OF TOURISM	BEN - MITUR
FUNDACIÓN TECNALIA RESEARCH & INNOVATION	BEN - TECNALIA	NECSTOUR	BEN - NECSTOUR
CITY DESTINATIONS ALLIANCE	BEN - CityDNA	INTELLERA	BEN - INTELLERA
ARCTUR	BEN - ARCTUR	INSTITUTO TECNOLÓGICO DE INFORMÁTICA	BEN - ITI
GMV SOLUCIONES GLOBALES INTERNET	BEN - GMV	AVORIS CENTRAL DIVISION	BEN - AVORIS
AUSTRIA TOURISM (OSTERREICH WERBUNG)	BEN – AUSTRIA TOURISM	EUROPEANA	BEN - EF
TURISMO ANDALUCIA	BEN – EPGTDA SA	AMADEUS SAS	BEN – AMADEUS SAS
PLEXUS TECH	BEN – PLEXUS TECH	TECNOLOGÍAS PLEXUS SL	AE - PLEXUS
FRAUNHOFER	BEN - FRAUNHOFER	HIBERUS TECNOLOGIAS DIFERENCIALES SL	BEN - HIBERUSTECH
HIBERUS IT DEVELOP	AE - HIBIT	UNPARALLEL INNOVATION	BEN - UNPARALLEL
PLEIADES CLUSTER	BEN - PLEIAD	UNI SYSTEMS SYSTMATA	AE - UNIS
THE DATA APPEAL COMPANY	BEN – DATA APPEAL CO	INDUSTRYINNOVATION CLUSTER SLOVAKIA	BEN - IIC
TOURISM SLOVENIA BOHINJ	BEN – TURIZEM BOHINJ	LAPLAND UNIVERSITY OF APPLIED SCIENCES	BEN – LAPLAND UAS
DISSET CONSULTORES	BEN - DISSET	UNIVERSITY ILLES BALEARS	BEN - UIB
ADQUIVER	BEN - ADQUIVER	ADQUIVER DATA & ADVANCED ANALYTICS, SL	AE - ADDATA
TRENITALIA	BEN - TRIT	TOURISM PORTUGAL	BEN – TURISMO PT
UNIVERSITY NOVA LISBOA	BEN - UNL	LIBELIUM LAB	BEN – LIBELIUM
MODUL UNIVERSITY VIENNA GMBH	AP - MODUL	YPOURGEIO TOURISMOU	AP - MINTUR
AGENCIA DE ESTRATEGIA TURÍSTICA DE LES ILLES BALEARS	AP - AETIB	STICHTING BREDA UNIVERSITY OF APPLIED SCIENCES	BEN - BUAS
FIWARE FOUNDATION EV	AP - FIWARE	ASOCIACIÓN INSTITUTO TECNOLÓGICO HOTELERO	BEN - ITH

Document name:	D4.2 First quarterly report on DEPLOYTOUR pilot implementation	Page:	1 of 53
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU
	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

This document translates some of the obligations from the grant agreement and in case of discrepancies, it is the grant agreement which prevails over this deliverable.

D4.2 First quarterly report on DEPLOYTOUR pilot implementation

Document Identification			
Status	Final	Due Date	31/12/2025
Version	V1.0	Submission Date	

Related WP	WP4	Document Reference	D4.2
Related Deliverable(s)	D4.3, D4.4, D4.5, D4.6, D4.7, D4.8, D4.9	Dissemination Level (*)	PU
Lead Partner	POLIMI	Lead Author	Margherita Maria Mancini
Contributors	Eleonora Lorenzini Federica Russo Margherita Maria Mancini Peio Oiz Arruti Dolores Ordóñez Tayrne Butler Ana Monice Bermejo Urška Starc Peceny Vesna Kobal Marie Texier Jonathan Huffstutler Liliana Beltrán Eeva Helameri Georgia Lignou Maria Pahoula	Reviewers	DATAAPPEAL

Document name:	D4.2 First quarterly report on DEPLOYTOUR pilot implementation	Page:	2 of 53	
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	
	Version:	1.0	Status:	Final

This document translates some of the obligations from the grant agreement and in case of discrepancies, it is the grant agreement which prevails over this deliverable.

Document Information

List of Contributors	
Name	Partner
Eleonora Lorenzini	Politecnico di Milano
Margherita Maria Mancini	Politecnico di Milano
Federica Russo	Politecnico di Milano
Ana Moniche Bermejo	Turismo Andaluz
Peio Oiz Arruti	Anysolution
Dolores Ordóñez	AnySolution
Tayrne Butler	AnySolution
Urška Starc Peceny	Arctur
Vesna Kobal	Arctur
Marie Texier	EONA-X
Jonathan Huffstutler	EONA-X
Liliana Beltrán	ITI
Eeva Helameri	Lapland UAS
Georgia Lignou	Pleiades
Maria Pahoula	Pleiades

Document History			
Version	Date	Change editors	Changes
0.1	30/11/25	Margherita Maria Mancini, Eleonora Lorenzini, Federica Russo	Initial version sent to reviewers
0.2	19/12/25	Margherita Maria Mancini, Eleonora Lorenzini, Federica Russo	Revised version based on reviewers' comments
1	29/12/2025	Tayrne Butler	Final formatting

Quality Control		
Role	Who (Partner short name)	Approval Date
Deliverable leader	POLIMI	22/12/2025
Project coordinator	AnySol	29/12/2025

Document name:	D4.2 First quarterly report on DEPLOYTOUR pilot implementation	Page:	3 of 53
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU
		Version:	1.0
		Status:	Final

This document translates some of the obligations from the grant agreement and in case of discrepancies, it is the grant agreement which prevails over this deliverable.

Table of Contents

Document Information	3
Table of Contents	4
List of Tables	6
List of Figures	7
List of Acronyms	8
Executive Summary	9
1. Introduction	10
1.1. Purpose of the Document	10
1.2. Structure of the Document	10
2. Overview of the activities carried out for pilots' implementation: M1-M13	11
2.1 Pilot coordination	11
2.2 Pilot implementation	12
2.2.1 Alignment with WP2 – Technical Group	12
2.2.2 Alignment with WP3 – Governance	13
2.3 Support services	14
2.4 Monitoring and evaluation	15
3. Pilots' progress report	16
3.1 Pilot 1: Sustainable Tourism Management of Alpine Tourism	16
3.1.1 Definition of purpose	16
3.1.2 Use case definition	17
3.1.3 Identification of data sources	19
3.1.4 Identification and involvement of stakeholders	22
3.2 Pilot 2 - Mature Destination Resiliency and Competitiveness	23
3.2.1 Definition of purpose	23
3.2.2 Use case definition	25
3.2.3 Identification of data sources	27
3.2.4 Identification and involvement of stakeholders	31
3.3 Pilot 3 - MICE sector support	33
3.3.1 Definition of purpose	33
3.3.2 Use case definition	34
3.3.3 Identification of data sources	36
3.3.4 Identification and involvement of stakeholders	37
3.4 Pilot 4 - Leveraging cultural heritage to diversify tourism offer: the case of Ano Syros (Greece)	39
3.4.1 Definition of purpose	39
3.4.2 Use case definition	41
3.4.3 Identification of data sources	43
3.4.4 Identification and involvement of stakeholders	46

Document name:	D4.2 First quarterly report on DEPLOYTOUR pilot implementation	Page:	4 of 53
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU
	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

This document translates some of the obligations from the grant agreement and in case of discrepancies, it is the grant agreement which prevails over this deliverable.

3.5	Pilot 5 – Empowering SMEs in Tourism through a Collaborative TravelTech	47
3.5.1	Definition of purpose	47
3.5.2	Use case definition	49
3.5.3	Identification of data sources	50
3.5.4	Identification and involvement of stakeholders.....	52
Conclusion.....		53

Document name:	D4.2 First quarterly report on DEPLOYTOUR pilot implementation	Page:	5 of 53
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU
	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

This document translates some of the obligations from the grant agreement and in case of discrepancies, it is the grant agreement which prevails over this deliverable.

List of Tables

Table 1. Involved partners (Pilot 1).....	16
Table 2. KPI Total number of use cases identified (Pilot 1)	18
Table 3. KPI Total number of data providers identified (Pilot 1)	20
Table 4. KPI Total number of datasets identified (Pilot 1)	20
Table 5. KPI Total number of datasets of non-open data identified (Pilot 1)	20
Table 6. Data sources identified (Pilot 1).....	21
Table 7. Involved partners (Pilot 2).....	24
Table 8. KPI Total number of use cases identified (Pilot 1).....	26
Table 9. KPI Total number of data providers identified (Pilot 2)	28
Table 10. KPI Total number of datasets identified (Pilot 2).....	29
Table 11. KPI Total number of datasets of non-open data identified (Pilot 2).....	29
Table 12. Data sources identified (Pilot 2).....	29
Table 13. Involved partners (Pilot 3).....	33
Table 14. KPI Total number of use cases identified (Pilot 3)	34
Table 15. KPI Total number of data providers identified (Pilot 3)	36
Table 16. KPI Total number of datasets identified (Pilot 3).....	36
Table 17. KPI Total number of datasets of non-open data identified (Pilot 3).....	37
Table 18. Data sources identified (Pilot 3).....	37
Table 19. Involved partners (Pilot 4).....	39
Table 20. KPI Total number of use cases identified (Pilot 4).....	41
Table 21. KPI Total number of data providers identified (Pilot 4)	43
Table 22. KPI Total number of datasets identified (Pilot 4).....	43
Table 23. KPI Total number of datasets of non-open data identified (Pilot 4).....	43
Table 24. Data sources identified (Pilot 4).....	44
Table 25. Involved partners (Pilot 5).....	47
Table 26. KPI Total number of use cases identified (Pilot 5)	49
Table 27. KPI Total number of data providers identified (Pilot 5)	50
Table 28. KPI Total number of datasets identified (Pilot 5).....	50
Table 29. KPI Total number of datasets of non-open data identified (Pilot 5).....	50
Table 30. Data sources identified (Pilot 5).....	51

Document name:	D4.2 First quarterly report on DEPLOYTOUR pilot implementation	Page:	6 of 53
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU
	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

This document translates some of the obligations from the grant agreement and in case of discrepancies, it is the grant agreement which prevails over this deliverable.

List of Figures

Figure 1. Pilots' action plan – Main phases 14

Document name:	D4.2 First quarterly report on DEPLOYTOUR pilot implementation	Page:	7 of 53
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU
	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

This document translates some of the obligations from the grant agreement and in case of discrepancies, it is the grant agreement which prevails over this deliverable.

List of Acronyms

Abbreviation/acronym	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
AR/VR	Augmented Reality/Virtual Reality
CC BY	Creative Commons Attribution
CC BY – NC-SA	Creative Commons Attribution–NonCommercial–ShareAlike
CSR	Corporate Social Responsibility
DMO	Destination Management Organisation
DP	Data Product
DPO	Data Product Offering
DS	DataSpace
ETDS	European Tourism Data Space
GIS	Geographic Information System
IDF	Île-de-France
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MICE	Meetings, Incentives, Conferences, and Exhibitions
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
OTA	Online Travel Agency
POI	Point of Interest
SMART	Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, and Time-bound
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
UC	Use Case
WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4	Work Package 1, Work Package 2, Work Package 3, Work Package 4

Document name:	D4.2 First quarterly report on DEPLOYTOUR pilot implementation	Page:	8 of 53
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU
	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

This document translates some of the obligations from the grant agreement and in case of discrepancies, it is the grant agreement which prevails over this deliverable.

Executive Summary

The implementation of the five use-case pilots is pivotal to the success of the DEPLOYTOUR project, as it will demonstrate the value of a European federated tourism data space in addressing major tourism challenges across different contexts.

This deliverable is the first quarterly report on pilots' implementation and covers both the activities carried out by the pilots' teams and their tangible results. It aims to report on all the different aspects characterising the road towards the implementation of the use cases, from the definition of strategic objectives to the practical actions. Both quantitative KPIs and extensive, qualitative descriptions are used to assess pilots' performance.

This document covers activities from M1 (October 2024) to M13 (October 2025).

Document name:	D4.2 First quarterly report on DEPLOYTOUR pilot implementation	Page:	9 of 53				
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status:	Final

This document translates some of the obligations from the grant agreement and in case of discrepancies, it is the grant agreement which prevails over this deliverable.

1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose of the Document

This document is an activity progress report and has the purpose of describing in detail, in the context of the DEPLOYTOUR project, the work done from the beginning of the project (M1) up until October 2025 (M13), aimed at the smooth implementation of the five pilots:

- Pilot 1: Sustainable Tourism Management of Alpine Tourism
- Pilot 2: Mature Destination Resiliency and Competitiveness
- Pilot 3: MICE sector support
- Pilot 4: Leveraging cultural heritage to diversify tourism offer: the case of Ano Syros (Greece)
- Pilot 5: Empowering SMEs in Tourism through a Collaborative TravelTech

Through this document, we aim to raise awareness of the work carried out within pilots' teams, aligned with each pilot's specific objectives, and of the surrounding coordination, support, and monitoring activities performed by Work Package 4 partners to ensure alignment with the project's general objectives. Moreover, we wish to emphasise the close interactions and exchanges with other Work Packages, as they are key to the success of the individual pilots and to the success of the European Tourism Data Space (ETDS) as a whole.

1.2. Structure of the Document

The document is divided into two main blocks:

Chapter 2: **Overview of the activities carried out for pilots' implementation: M1-M13**

This section presents a general overview of pilots' road towards complete implementation, describing coordination activities (Paragraph 2.1), the overall working plan followed by all pilot teams in coordination with technical and governance WPs (Paragraph 2.2), the support services (Paragraph 2.3) developed and tested to assist the pilots in the process, and the monitoring and performance evaluation system (Paragraph 2.4) structured and validated to ensure a flow of continuous measurement and feedback throughout the project.

Chapter 3: **Pilots' progress report**

Every pilot represents key challenges and priorities of the Tourism ecosystem, declined in specific territories, industries and communities. This is why it is crucial to account for the process followed by each pilot team to address context-specific issues and needs, ensure alignment with local key stakeholders, and work to reach their own objectives. A detailed description of each pilots' state of implementation is the core of this section. In particular, a Paragraph will be dedicated to the progress report of one pilot (Pilot 1: Paragraph 3.1, Pilot 2: Paragraph 3.2, Pilot 3: Paragraph 3.3, Pilot 4: Paragraph 3.4, Pilot 5: Paragraph 3.5). This report describes pilots' definition of purpose, the definition of ETDS use cases, the identification of data sources, and the identification and engagement of key stakeholders. All these reported activities have laid the foundation for the start of technical implementation and data exploitation.

Document name:	D4.2 First quarterly report on DEPLOYTOUR pilot implementation	Page:	10 of 53
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU
	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

This document translates some of the obligations from the grant agreement and in case of discrepancies, it is the grant agreement which prevails over this deliverable.

2. Overview of the activities carried out for pilots' implementation: M1-M13

2.1 Pilot coordination

Each pilot represents different typologies of tourism destinations, tourism offers, and data-sharing approaches, requiring a high level of customisation in strategic and management approaches. Nonetheless, each aligns with DEPLOYTOUR's broader vision and objectives and will be fundamental to demonstrating the potential of the ETDS. Balancing these two components (the *micro* as well as the *macro*-objectives of each pilot) requires serious and attentive work of coordination.

Pilot coordination activities conducted from M1 to M13 fall into three main groups: first, those related to the preparatory phase leading to pilot implementation (M1-M12); second, those concerned with the overview of the first phases of pilot implementation (M13); and third, those that ensure day-to-day coordination.

Preparatory phase (M1-M12)

During the first year, the pilots have worked closely with other WPs and with the WP and project coordinators to prepare the field for subsequent implementation. Coordination activities were aimed at:

1. Ensure the refinement of pilots' objectives
2. Clarify partners' roles and contributions in each pilot
3. Supervise the definition of use cases to be implemented
4. Support the identification of pilots' data sources and requirements

The results of each pilot's preparatory work will be described in Chapter 3.

Pilots' objectives had to meet the SMART criteria: Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, and Time-bound. Overall, the preparatory phase ensured the clear identification of the 4Ws: Who, What, Why and When.

Pilots participated in stakeholder engagement and the preliminary analysis of their context, available resources, and skills. The corpus of common preparatory knowledge and awareness generated in this phase has been formalised in internal documentation (e.g., use case descriptions, pilot descriptions, boards for regular updates, KPI definitions) available to the entire consortium.

Moreover, inter-pilot meetings were launched to enhance cooperation and alignment with the macro-objectives, encouraging pilots to share best practices, issues, and updates.

Beginning of the pilot implementation phase (M13)

October 2025 marked the start of the implementation phase, which will deliver the identified use cases via the ETDS. This is a crucial moment for the project and requires ongoing collaboration with the technical and governance groups. Ensuring the fluidity and continuity of these exchanges is the primary coordination objective for this period.

Continuously mapping and updating the maturity level of each use case is fundamental. This is why each pilot reports, for each use case defined:

- Data providers and data consumers for each data exchange
- Needs to be addressed for each data exchange
- Current state (completely validated / ongoing validation / explored hypothesis)

Document name:	D4.2 First quarterly report on DEPLOYTOUR pilot implementation	Page:	11 of 53
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU
	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

This document translates some of the obligations from the grant agreement and in case of discrepancies, it is the grant agreement which prevails over this deliverable.

Day-by-day coordination (M1-M13)

Coordinating the pilots requires day-to-day communication streams to collect updates, feedback, questions, and issues; provide missing information; ensure work is carried out in line with deadlines and quality standards; and keep partners informed and involved.

2.2 Pilot implementation

2.2.1 Alignment with WP2 – Technical Group

In liaison with the technical group, pilots identified and detailed their data sources and requirements, and, in a subsequent phase, identified data products and DPOs (Data Product Offerings).

Data sources identification

Pilots made sure to collect the following information for each data source:

- Data owner
- Prospected usage
- Availability level (national/regional/local/other)
- Current availability state for the project (available/potential/incomplete/missing)
- Accessibility (open access / paid access)
- Technical specifications

Data products and DPOs definition

Pilots have worked on the identification and definition of data products, which are composed of multiple data sources; there can be one or more data product offerings per use case. The data product offering is the implementation of the data product in DEPLOYTOUR and determines how a data product becomes a data asset. The data offering could be implemented in the data space connector and handles usage control, formats, data asset publication, and data asset catalogue. In other words, it defines how the data product is offered to the data space.

For each identified DPO, the following questions were addressed:

- *Can you provide a name for your data product offering?*
- *Can you provide a functional description of your data product offering?*
- *What is the scope of the data offering in terms of tourism?*
- *What is the geographical data product offering scope?*
- *What is your data product offering type?*
- *What are the data sources that will use this kind of data product offering?*
- *Is there personal data involved in your data product offering, or are there any ethical considerations? Could this data lead to the re-identification of an individual when combined with available data from the same project or publicly available data?*
- *Is your current data model (if any) in conformance with existing standard(s)? If yes, which? – Examples: CSV, AIXM*
- *What is the underlying protocol used to transfer your data product? – Examples: online sharing, API over HTTPS*
- *When integrating a data product (back end) with a connector, are there specific access control mechanisms or workflows needed to publish the data product? – Example: need for an API key*
- *Are there performance concerns about your data product, such as latency, high volumes, or certain service level agreement(s)?*
- *Self-assess your data product offering maturity.*

Document name:	D4.2 First quarterly report on DEPLOYTOUR pilot implementation	Page:	12 of 53
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU
	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

This document translates some of the obligations from the grant agreement and in case of discrepancies, it is the grant agreement which prevails over this deliverable.

Current work is focused on identifying, also in liaison with the governance team:

Data Product Governance: to identify standard practices in data management and product compliance, including industry/domain standards and governance models relevant for various use cases. Data product owners should outline their trust-building processes to guide our decision on supporting identity management and data sovereignty, and to determine whether DEPLOYTOUR needs a fully managed trust model. Such work requires providing, for each DPO identified, clear answers to the following questions:

- Which data model (if any) should/would you like to be used? A new data format might be imposed by future legislation or initiative
- Are there any requirements for the authentication and identification of participants?
- Are there any requirements for access control to the data product?

Business models: to determine how diverse the participants' business expectations are and how the data will be exchanged (with which conditions and criteria, both economic and non-economic). We also want to determine if a shared business model is viable or rather fosters an ecosystem of value returns. DEPLOYTOUR should provide the necessary building blocks to support this diversity. Such work requires providing, for each DPO identified, clear answers at least to the following questions, while leaving room for additional aspects to be explored in greater depth as needed:

- What is the expected/intended business model for the DPO and relevant restrictions?
- What is the value proposition (if any) of the data product offering?
- Does the data product offering fall under local legislation that might differ from and/or precede EU and foreign legislation?

Data space federation: to identify cases in which data products are already part of an existing data space. The information must help us determine the most flexible and sustainable way to integrate them into DEPLOYTOUR.

The alignment effort with the technical group has included:

- Joint sessions with WP2 to validate data availability and potential pipelines
- Early-stage assessment of data access mechanisms (e.g. APIs, bulk downloads, real-time feeds)
- Review of data quality and readiness for ingestion into interoperable components

2.2.2 Alignment with WP3 – Governance

In liaison with the governance group, pilots have engaged in interactive training activities to gain an in-depth understanding of the characteristics of roles in a data space. Such workshops have laid the foundation for a shared understanding of the core roles that must be identified and clarified for each use case.

Covered aspects included:

- The role of data providers
- The role of data consumers
- The role of the coordinator
- The role of application providers
- The rulebook
- The data and metadata management
- The platform and core service provider

Document name:	D4.2 First quarterly report on DEPLOYTOUR pilot implementation	Page:	13 of 53
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU
	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

This document translates some of the obligations from the grant agreement and in case of discrepancies, it is the grant agreement which prevails over this deliverable.

2.3 Support services

The Support Services Catalogue aims to facilitate the pilots’ journey by providing a comprehensive set of resources, practical guidance, and capacity-building opportunities. The ultimate purpose of these services is to ensure that all pilots, regardless of their technical readiness or business maturity, receive appropriate and timely support throughout their lifecycle. This Catalogue is an interactive, living portfolio that evolves alongside the pilots’ needs.

During the first quarter of operations, the first version of the Support Service Catalogue was launched, integrating three main service types: Resources (key documentation and reference materials), Training (practical knowledge), and Mentoring (specific, one-to-one support). Regarding **Resources**, two key documents were developed to structure and guide the pilots’ support process:

1. **The Living Q&A Document**, updated monthly, which reports clear answers to pilots’ questions
2. **The Onboarding Document** (WP4 Milestone: MS8), which outlines the ETDS onboarding process, requisites and guidelines. Both documents were prepared in close coordination with WP2, WP3, and WP5 to ensure full alignment with technical and governance frameworks.

The Training Programme was defined in accordance with the Action Plan and shared with the pilots. During this period, the first **phase** was completed and delivered to the pilots (the plan includes 7 phases). **The 1st phase’s** main objective was to understand the onboarding process and self-assessment methodology. This phase included a virtual Kickoff session held in October 2025 that addressed the evolution of Data Product Offerings (DPOs) and included a practical, hands-on exercise.

Figure 1. Pilots’ action plan – Main phases

Finally, for the Mentoring programme, the identification and assignment of mentors across the three pillars (technical, governance, and business) were completed. Each pilot has been assigned specific mentors from both WP2 (technical) and WP3 (governance), who will actively participate in their activities and provide implementation support.

Overall, these activities have laid the foundation for the Support Service Catalogue (WP4 Milestone: MS9), aligning resources, training, and mentoring with the pilots’ operational needs and preparing them for transition to the implementation phase.

Document name:	D4.2 First quarterly report on DEPLOYTOUR pilot implementation	Page:	14 of 53
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU
	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

This document translates some of the obligations from the grant agreement and in case of discrepancies, it is the grant agreement which prevails over this deliverable.

2.4 Monitoring and evaluation

The monitoring efforts have focused on developing and describing a system of quantitative KPIs and qualitative approaches to evaluate the performance of the ETDS pilot use cases, aimed at measuring progress, impact, and success factors during the implementation phase.

The KPIs have been selected and structured in accordance with specific criteria. In particular, each KPI is:

- **Comprehensive yet concise.** They should provide a broad view of the project's development while remaining synthetic.
- **Common to all pilots.** They should be measurable by all pilots, regardless of their specific use cases and context.
- **Relevant both at the micro level (pilot and use case) and at the macro level (dataspace).** Each KPI should provide information on both pilots' progress and results, and, at the aggregated level, the progress of the dataspace implementation as a whole.
- **Simple to measure.** Each pilot team should be able to easily access the data and information needed to measure the KPIs.
- **Intuitive to interpret.** Each project stakeholder should intuitively understand what information each KPI brings.

KPIs for each pilot are reported in this document.

Document name:	D4.2 First quarterly report on DEPLOYTOUR pilot implementation	Page:	15 of 53
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU
	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

This document translates some of the obligations from the grant agreement and in case of discrepancies, it is the grant agreement which prevails over this deliverable.

3. Pilots' progress report

3.1 Pilot 1: Sustainable Tourism Management of Alpine Tourism

3.1.1 Definition of purpose

The Alpine region faces increasing pressure from tourism, including overcrowding in natural and protected areas, environmental degradation, climate change impacts, and insufficient awareness among tourists of sustainable travel practices. High-traffic seasons and major international events—such as ski competitions and cultural festivals—further strain local infrastructure and ecosystems, particularly in cross-border areas where coordination is limited.

This pilot's objective is to establish a data-driven approach to sustainable tourism management across the cross-border Alpine region, with a focus on Austria, Italy, and Slovenia. It aims at promoting eco-friendly tourism by enabling real-time monitoring of visitor flows, assessing environmental impact, and supporting informed decision-making through integrated data.

The following key activities are pursuing these objectives:

- Identify and integrate diverse data sources.
- Harmonise data through the European Tourism Data Space (ETDS) for seamless sharing and analysis.
- Implement the FLOWS dashboard for real-time monitoring of tourism flows and environmental impact.
- Conduct international testing and validation in Slovenia and Austria to ensure scalability and interoperability.

Cross-border data integration and cooperation are key components of the pilot, which focuses on extending the FLOWS application beyond Slovenia. By integrating Austrian (Carinthia) and Italian (Friuli-Venezia Giulia) destinations, the pilot promotes a harmonised approach to visitor management and sustainability.

Several benefits arise from cross-border integration:

- **Comparative dashboards and event synchronisation** enable cross-border monitoring of tourism trends and visitor pressure across the Alpine region, supporting coordinated management of shared peaks—especially during international sports events.
- **Establishing shared formats and protocols for data sharing** through ETDS. This cross-border dimension ensures that lessons learned and solutions developed in one region can be adapted and scaled across the Alpine tourism ecosystem.

3.1.1.1 Involved partners, roles and responsibilities

Table 1. Involved partners (Pilot 1)

Partner	Value added to the pilot (tools, know-how, ...)	Role and expectations
ARCTUR	Technical expertise in the implementation of connectors Experiences from other data spaces (i.e. TEMS) Coordination skills	<i>Pilot lead:</i> Developer of the FLOWS application (dashboard) Data integration in the FLOWS application Data provider (IoT data)

Document name:	D4.2 First quarterly report on DEPLOYTOUR pilot implementation	Page:	16 of 53
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU
	Version:	0.1	Status: Draft pending approval

This document translates some of the obligations from the grant agreement and in case of discrepancies, it is the grant agreement which prevails over this deliverable.

TOURISM BOHINJ	Deep knowledge of the Slovenian Alpine context and stakeholders	<i>Key Partner involved in the development of UC1:</i> Coordination with Slovenian stakeholders: the Julian Alps Community, Triglav National Park, and the Slovenian Tourist Board. Definition of needs.
AUSTRIA TOURISM	Deep knowledge of the Austrian context and stakeholder	<i>Key Partner involved in the development of UC2:</i> Data partner Coordination with Austrian stakeholders
EONA-X	Expertise in data space ecosystems Access to data sources Experience in use cases	<i>Participant:</i> Data space partner. Supporting data exchanges. Providing data products
CITY DNA	Relevant network of European DMOs	<i>Participant:</i> Support networking. Promote solution scalability.
THE DATA APPEAL COMPANY	Relevant data products and data tourism expertise	<i>Participant:</i> Data provider for the cross-border section.
TRENITALIA	Extensive knowledge of the Italian context, especially regarding train transportation	<i>Participant:</i> Data partner. Onboarding of datasets through Pilot1 with the possibility of use cases.

3.1.2 Use case definition

Use Case 1 FLOWS Julian Alps (UC1) focuses on sustainable tourism management in the Alpine region spanning Slovenia, Austria, and Italy. The FLOWS platform integrates real-time and historical data from multiple sources to monitor visitor flows and environmental impact. It enables DMOs to visualise tourism trends, assess carrying capacities, and make data-driven decisions to prevent overcrowding.

The solution supports proactive management during peak seasons and major events, such as ski competitions, enhancing cross-border coordination. By harmonising data standards and enabling cross-border dashboards, FLOWS promotes sustainable development, reduces pressure on fragile ecosystems, and improves visitor experience through better infrastructure planning and multilingual digital services.

The definition of UC1 was grounded in an internal needs assessment that identified critical challenges, including visitor concentration during peak seasons and major events, infrastructure overload, and fragmented data governance across borders. These internal insights highlighted the **need for real-time monitoring, data integration, and cross-border coordination to support sustainable tourism management**. Stakeholder involvement was central to shaping the use case, with active engagement from DMOs, local municipalities, and tourism associations. Their input confirmed the demand for actionable, harmonised data and validated the FLOWS platform's relevance as a shared solution.

Priority settings were established based on the region's high tourism pressure, strong institutional collaboration, and readiness to adopt data-driven tools. The Julian Alps

Document name:	D4.2 First quarterly report on DEPLOYTOUR pilot implementation	Page:	17 of 53
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU
	Version:	0.1	Status: Draft pending approval

This document translates some of the obligations from the grant agreement and in case of discrepancies, it is the grant agreement which prevails over this deliverable.

Community was prioritised for its existing data infrastructure, political commitment, and strategic location at the crossroads of Slovenia, Austria, and Italy, making it an ideal pilot for scalable, cross-border sustainable tourism solutions.

The definition of **Use Case 2 followed a structured**, evidence-based and stakeholder-driven process. An initial internal needs assessment by Austria Tourism identified a lack of harmonised sustainability information for Alpine tours and a strong demand from destinations, hotels and outdoor platforms to guide visitors towards environmentally responsible behaviour. Feasibility checks examined available environmental, mobility and tourism datasets and confirmed the technical viability of developing a cross-border sustainability scoring model. A multi-stage stakeholder process is about to validate and refine these needs: the first stakeholder workshop (37 participants from tourism, mobility, climate and conservation organisations) explored requirements, data availability, use cases, risks and expected benefits, confirming a broad need for a sustainability scoring model, API-based integration, and contextual data. Additional bilateral consultations are helping to identify critical data gaps, priority regions, and cross-border alignment opportunities. Based on stakeholder priorities, feasibility, scalability within the Tourism Data Space, and cross-border relevance, the sustainability-scoring use case for Alpine tours was selected as the primary UC2 focus.

Table 2. KPI Total number of use cases identified (Pilot 1)

KPI 1: Total number of use cases identified	2
• Use cases in the phase: JUST HYPOTHESIS	0
• Use cases in the phase: ONGOING VALIDATION	2
• Use cases in the phase: COMPLETELY VALIDATED	0
• Use cases in the phase: ONBOARDING COMPLETED	0
• Use cases in the phase: DATA SHARING COMPLETED	0

Use Case 1: FLOWS Julian Alps

Needs addressed. Addressing tourist overcrowding and environmental strain in Alpine ecosystems, improving cross-border coordination, enhancing real-time decision-making for DMOs in the Julian Alps, and enabling sustainable tourism through data-driven management. Overcoming fragmented data governance, inconsistent data quality, and limited multilingual, real-time services for tourists across Slovenia, Austria, and Italy.

Functional description. FLOWS application (FLOWS) provides a real-time, cross-border dashboard for monitoring tourist flows, cross-border events' impact, accommodation occupancy, weather impacts, and trail usage in the Julian Alps. It enables DMOs to assess carrying capacities, anticipate peak demand, and implement proactive measures such as crowd dispersal and sustainable mobility promotion. The system integrates analytics and tools to support strategic planning.

FLOWS implementation is currently in the validation phase for the Julian Alps Community.

Sustainability focus. FLOWS supports sustainable Alpine tourism by reducing pressure on fragile ecosystems and advancing regional sustainability goals through real-time data, cross-border dashboards, and coordinated event management.

Document name:	D4.2 First quarterly report on DEPLOYTOUR pilot implementation	Page:	18 of 53
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU
	Version:	0.1	Status: Draft pending approval

This document translates some of the obligations from the grant agreement and in case of discrepancies, it is the grant agreement which prevails over this deliverable.

Involved data providers. The Data Appeal Company (events impact, OTA saturation and prices datapack), Statistical offices (SI, AT, IT), Arctur (Trail Visitor data)

Data consumers. Arctur (events impact data, OTA saturation and prices datapack, statistical data for FLOWS application).

Use Case 2: Sustainability Calculator by Austrian Tourism

Needs addressed. Tourism in Alpine protected areas is facing increasing environmental pressure from rising numbers of hikers and off-trail activities (hiking, biking, skiing), and limited awareness of sustainable behaviour. These pressures contribute to soil erosion, vegetation loss, wildlife disturbance, biodiversity decline, and growing conflict with local communities. Currently, no unified model exists to assess tour sustainability or to provide harmonised sustainability information to tourists.

DMOs, hotels and platform providers lack a consistent source of environmental and visitor-related data to guide travellers toward more sustainable route choices. Existing apps do not offer dynamic sustainability indicators (e.g., ecological impact, visitor pressure, tour alternatives), and cross-border regions lack shared monitoring systems. The project therefore addresses fragmented data access, gaps in cross-border interoperability, and the need for data-driven decision-making to support sustainability goals in Alpine regions.

Functional description. The Digital Sustainability Calculator is a cross-border digital model that calculates the sustainability score of tours in Alpine protected areas. The model should integrate historical data, dynamic visitor forecasts, environmental impact indicators, and mobility information to generate a dynamic sustainability score for a selected route. Beyond scoring, the model should provide information on environmentally appropriate behaviour (e.g., staying on the path, fire restrictions, wildlife protection), identify environmental risks, and suggest more sustainable alternative routes.

The service will be developed as an API-first model that can be integrated into existing apps, booking platforms, tourism systems, and DMO tools (B2B2C). It will support destinations by providing benchmarking, sustainability monitoring, and situational awareness based on live data streams.

The model will be developed for at least two countries (Austria and Slovenia) and will demonstrate the benefits of sharing tourism, environmental, and mobility data via the European Tourism Data Space. A functioning prototype will be connected to the ETDS.

Involved data providers. Austria Tourism (Tourism Infrastructure Data/ MataAPI), OutdoorActive (Tour Data tbc.)

Data consumers. Hiking and outdoor apps, hotels and tourism platforms integrating sustainability scores, DMOs and regional authorities, protected area administrations, policy makers (and tourists receiving sustainability insights and alternative route suggestions via integrated applications).

3.1.3 Identification of data sources

UC1: The identification and revision of data sources for UC1 followed a structured process grounded in stakeholder needs, feasibility, and alignment with EU data standards. The initial needs assessment identified key challenges in Alpine tourism: overcrowding, environmental strain, and fragmented data. Stakeholder consultations with DMOs, municipalities, and data providers in Slovenia, Austria, and Italy mapped existing data assets and gaps. Data sources

Document name:	D4.2 First quarterly report on DEPLOYTOUR pilot implementation	Page:	19 of 53
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU
	Version:	0.1	Status: Draft pending approval

This document translates some of the obligations from the grant agreement and in case of discrepancies, it is the grant agreement which prevails over this deliverable.

were selected based on relevance, availability, and interoperability potential, covering accommodation records (statistical offices in SI, AT, IT), trail-visit data (IoT sensor real-time data), event-impact data, OTA saturation, and price data (The Data Appeal Company). Cooperation with the technical group (WP2) also enabled the initial definitions of data product offerings. Iterative validation with local partners refined data selection, prioritising real-time, multilingual, and cross-border-accessible datasets, while addressing gaps with synthetic data where necessary.

UC2: The UC2 Team is still identifying and assessing data sources. The focus was primarily on identifying similar data sources available on the Austrian and Slovenian sides (e.g., number of alpine Accidents, Tour data from Outdoor Active).

The Sustainability Calculator requires interoperable environmental, geospatial, mobility, and tourism datasets to evaluate the sustainability of tours. Initial mapping confirmed fragmented availability, particularly regarding protected area boundaries, trail conditions, and real-time visitor flows.

Austria Tourism is about to evaluate relevant datasets from environmental agencies, national parks, tourism platforms (e.g., MetaAPI, OutdoorActive, The Data Appeal Company), statistical offices, climate services (ZAMG, ARSO), and mobility providers. Priority was given to datasets offering reliable geodata (trails, zoning), environmental indicators (biodiversity, vegetation state, water impact), weather and climate data, OTA saturation, and mobility information such as public transport schedules or parking usage.

Throughout the process, the technical partners ensured compliance with ETDS data models, metadata standards, and API-based access. The resulting shortlist includes available datasets, as well as sources that require further validation and onboarding in the next phase. The identified data providers represent key institutional and technical sources essential for cross-border sustainable tourism management in the Julian Alps. The inclusion of statistical offices (Slovenia, Austria, Italy) ensures reliable, harmonised, and open data on tourism flows, forming the backbone of the FLOWS dashboard. Arctur's IoT sensor data enables real-time monitoring of trail usage. The Data Appeal Company contributes forecasted event data, which is critical for proactive planning, though it remains proprietary.

Table 3. KPI Total number of data providers identified (Pilot 1)

KPI 2: Total number of DATA PROVIDERS identified	16
• <i>Data providers in the phase: JUST HYPOTHESIS</i>	4
• <i>Data providers in the phase: ONGOING VALIDATION</i>	10
• <i>Data providers in the phase: COMPLETELY VALIDATED</i>	2
• <i>Data providers in the phase: ONBOARDING COMPLETED</i>	0
• <i>Data providers in the phase: DATA SHARING COMPLETED</i>	0

Table 4. KPI Total number of datasets identified (Pilot 1)

KPI 3: Total number of DATASETS identified for sharing	16
• <i>Datasets in the phase: JUST HYPOTHESIS</i>	3
• <i>Datasets in the phase: ONGOING VALIDATION</i>	11
• <i>Datasets in the phase: COMPLETELY VALIDATED</i>	2
• <i>Datasets in the phase: ONBOARDING COMPLETED</i>	0
• <i>Datasets in the phase: DATA SHARING COMPLETED</i>	0

Table 5. KPI Total number of datasets of non-open data identified (Pilot 1)

Document name:	D4.2 First quarterly report on DEPLOYTOUR pilot implementation	Page:	20 of 53
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU
	Version:	0.1	Status:
			Draft pending approval

KPI 4: Total number of DATASETS of NON-OPEN DATA identified for sharing	7
• Datasets in the phase: <i>JUST HYPOTHESIS</i>	2
• Datasets in the phase: <i>ONGOING VALIDATION</i>	3
• Datasets in the phase: <i>COMPLETELY VALIDATED</i>	2
• Datasets in the phase: <i>ONBOARDING COMPLETED</i>	0
• Datasets in the phase: <i>DATA SHARING COMPLETED</i>	0

Table 6. Data sources identified (Pilot 1)

Data source	Relative use cases	Usage	Accessibility (Open/Proprietary)
The Data Appeal Company	UC1	Planning tourism flows through cross-border regions: 1) predicted events attendances 2) predicted events spending (F&B, hospitality, transportation) 3) details of the events 4) OTA saturation and prices	Proprietary
Statistical data - Slovenia	UC1, UC2	Planning and monitoring tourism flows	Open
Statistical data – Austria (Carinthia)	UC1, UC2	Planning and monitoring tourism flows	Open
Statistical data Italy (Friuli Venezia Giulia)	UC1, UC2	Planning and monitoring tourism flows	Open
Arctur Trail Visitor (IoT sensor data)	UC1, UC2	Planning and monitoring tourism flows	Open, Proprietary
Austria Tourism (Touristic infrastructure data)	UC2	Basic information on tours that is planned to be expanded with a dynamic indicator	Open, Proprietary with detailed texts and pictures
OutdoorActive	UC2	Basic tour information in Slovenia	Open, Proprietary
Digitalise the Planet	UC2	Structured, machine-readable data on protected areas and visitor regulations	Open
INSPIRE Geoportal Austria	UC2	Structured, machine-readable data on protected areas and visitor regulations	Open
Trenitalia	UC1, UC2	Planning and monitoring tourism flows	Proprietary
Geosphere / ARSO	UC2	Weather, climate	Open, Proprietary
National Park authorities / Digitise the planet	UC2	Protected zones, rules	Open
Municipalities / DMOs	UC2	Accommodation & event data	Proprietary
INSPIRE / Copernicus / GTIF	UC2	Geospatial data	Open, Proprietary
European Trails	UC2	Trails in Europe	Proprietary

Document name:	D4.2 First quarterly report on DEPLOYTOUR pilot implementation	Page:	21 of 53
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU
	Version:	0.1	Status: Draft pending approval

This document translates some of the obligations from the grant agreement and in case of discrepancies, it is the grant agreement which prevails over this deliverable.

Data.gv.at	UC2	Various open data	Open
------------	-----	-------------------	------

3.1.4 Identification and involvement of stakeholders

Stakeholder identification was based on sector, influence, interest, and role in the tourism data ecosystem. Criteria included institutional relevance, data ownership, decision-making power, and alignment with sustainability and cross-border cooperation goals. Activities included stakeholder mapping workshops, targeted interviews with DMOs and public authorities, and coordination meetings with national and regional tourism bodies.

UC1 key stakeholders include:

- Julian Alps Community (12 municipalities) - users of the final solution (FLOWS Dashboard).
- Triglav National Park, user of the final solution (FLOWS Dashboard),
- Arctur – pilot lead, technical partner for implementation of dashboard, data provider, and data user.
- Turizem Bohinj, coordinator of local stakeholders, user of final solution (FLOWS Dashboard), participating in the definition of user needs,
- Slovenian Tourist Board – strategic alliance.
-

These stakeholders are critical for data access, real-time monitoring, and cross-border coordination, ensuring the pilot’s scalability and impact.

Stakeholder identification for UC2 followed a structured process based on thematic relevance, data ownership, regulatory responsibilities, and the ability to support sustainable visitor management in Alpine protected areas. Key criteria included the availability of environmental and mobility data, operational responsibility for trail and nature management, and the potential to validate or use the Sustainability Calculator.

Austria Tourism conducted bilateral meetings, a large cross-sector stakeholder workshop, and follow-up consultations involving tourism boards, nature conservation authorities, national park administrations, environmental NGOs, outdoor platforms, mobility providers, and technology partners. These activities clarified data availability, governance requirements, and expectations for the model’s functionality.

Core stakeholders include national park authorities (e.g., Hohe Tauern, Triglav), regional DMOs, OutdoorActive and other tour-data platforms, environmental agencies (Geosphere, ARSO), mobility partners, and municipalities responsible for trail maintenance and zoning. Their involvement is essential for accessing geodata, environmental indicators, trail information, and visitor flow data, as well as for validating scoring logic and ensuring operational relevance.

The consultations confirmed strong stakeholder support for a transparent, scalable scoring model and highlighted the need for clear governance and data-quality standards. Engagement will continue throughout model development to refine requirements, secure data contributions, and prepare for cross-border testing.

Document name:	D4.2 First quarterly report on DEPLOYTOUR pilot implementation	Page:	22 of 53	
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	
	Version:	0.1	Status:	Draft pending approval

This document translates some of the obligations from the grant agreement and in case of discrepancies, it is the grant agreement which prevails over this deliverable.

3.2 Pilot 2 - Mature Destination Resiliency and Competitiveness

3.2.1 Definition of purpose

This pilot strengthens the sustainability and competitiveness of mature tourism destinations (Andalusia, the Canary Islands, and the Balearic Islands) by leveraging data to improve tourism management. It integrates sustainability indicators and operational data (from private data such as PMS and other sources, marketing platforms, data from public entities and official statistics) into destination and companies' decision-making.

Through data sharing and interoperability, the pilot helps destinations monitor resource use, visitor flows, and economic, social, environmental, and territorial impacts, and adjust marketing and planning actions accordingly, aligned with the destination's strategies. It shows in practice how data spaces can connect public and private information to support more balanced, efficient, and sustainable tourism management.

3.2.1.1 SMART Objectives

The objective of this pilot is to apply a data-driven approach to improve the sustainability, competitiveness, and resilience of mature tourism destinations such as Andalusia, the Balearic Islands, and the Canary Islands. The pilot will embed sustainability and redistribution criteria into the daily decision-making of DMOs, destination managers, and tourism SMEs, using the European Tourism Data Space (ETDS) as the core data-sharing environment.

The pilot will identify a set of sustainability data and calculate indicators and metrics to achieve regional-level KPIs, focusing on their practical use to support the redistribution of tourism flows over time and to balance areas in terms of occupancy, economic performance, or environmental protection. These indicators will be integrated into operational and decision-making processes and marketing workflows, enabling destinations to monitor visitor pressure, resource use, and seasonality while aligning actions with sustainability strategies.

Data-sharing mechanisms among tourism stakeholders (hotels, travel companies, administrations, DMOs, observatories, or marketing agencies) will be established to provide consistent, actionable insights. The pilot shows how interoperable data and shared governance models can enhance decision-making and collaboration across public and private actors, supporting a more balanced and adaptive management of tourism-related processes across the tourism ecosystem.

By doing so, the pilot aims to demonstrate how data interoperability and sustainability integration can drive smarter, more resilient, and competitive tourism models in Europe's mature destinations.

The pilot is developed by two use cases with specific objectives:

Use Case 1: Sustainability, Redistribution and Data-Driven Campaigns

- Creates a unified, data-driven marketing approach for mature destinations by integrating PMS, sustainability, and digital marketing data.
- Helps identify and attract high-value, low-impact tourist segments to align profitability with sustainability goals.
- Delivers real-time analytics to support decision-making and coordinate public-private marketing actions.
- Improves competitiveness through better targeting, resource optimisation, and a shift toward holistic ROI, including environmental factors.

Document name:	D4.2 First quarterly report on DEPLOYTOUR pilot implementation	Page:	23 of 53
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU
	Version:	0.1	Status: Draft pending approval

This document translates some of the obligations from the grant agreement and in case of discrepancies, it is the grant agreement which prevails over this deliverable.

Use Case 2: Sustainability and Impact Management

- Real-time monitor of tourism impact across four axes: Economic | Social | Environmental | Territorial.
- Provide local tourism authorities and DMOs with integrated, near-real-time data addressed to data-driven decision making.
- Support balanced, resilient, and sustainable destination management.

3.2.1.2 Involved partners, roles and responsibilities

Table 7. Involved partners (Pilot 2)

Partners UC1	Value added to the pilot (tools, know-how, ...)	Role and expectations
Turismo Andaluz (EPGTDA SA)	Andalusian DMO with extensive experience in sustainability indicators, tourism intelligence, and data governance.	Leads pilot two and oversees the direct implementation of the use case in Andalucía , providing managerial and technical support, supplying data sources (PMS, campaign data, sustainability metrics), and validating results for operational deployment.
NECSTouR (Network of European Regions for Sustainable and Competitive Tourism)	Brings managerial and technical expertise in coordinating multi-regional projects and developing data-driven tourism governance models.	Involved in the implementation of the pilot in Andalucía , providing managerial (defining requirements, helping to manage stakeholders) and technical support (data gathering, data analysis, sustainable indicators definition and calculation), and validating results for operational deployment.
AdQuiver	Specialist in digital marketing analytics and data integration from PMS and online platforms.	Collaborates on the integration and testing of data from PMS, digital marketing, and sustainability sources to produce actionable insights and transition marketing strategies from ROAS to ROI-driven approaches.
Partners UC2	Value added to the pilot (tools, know-how, ...)	Role and expectations
AnySolution	AnySolution is a European leader in tourism innovation, combining deep sector expertise with data spaces, smart-destination strategies, and advanced analytics to help public and private organisations make	Leads the implementation of the use case in the Balearic Islands . Ensures full interoperability and develops the dashboard to visualise and manage data within the

Document name:	D4.2 First quarterly report on DEPLOYTOUR pilot implementation	Page:	24 of 53
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU
		Version:	0.1
		Status:	Draft pending approval

This document translates some of the obligations from the grant agreement and in case of discrepancies, it is the grant agreement which prevails over this deliverable.

	better decisions and enhance visitor experiences.	European Tourism Data Space.
Universitat de les Illes Balears (UIB)	Academic and technical expertise in data analytics and sustainability research.	Supports the Balearic Islands pilot by providing relevant data and technical knowledge to assist stakeholders with the implementation, provision, availability, and validation of data.
AVORIS	One of the main global tourism actors and data contributors.	Acts as a data provider , supplying relevant tourism-related datasets for integration within the pilot.

3.2.2 Use case definition

The definition of Use Case 1 builds on the work of Turismo de Andalucía, which has developed a system of sustainability indicators (economic, social, and environmental) within the TSI project funded by the European Commission, with support from the OECD. An internal assessment identified marketing and promotion as key areas where these indicators could be applied to enable real-time campaign monitoring and align marketing actions with sustainability KPIs.

AdQuiver, a partner specialised in adtech and tourism intelligence, contributes its technological expertise to the design and implementation of a system for launching and tracking sustainability-based marketing campaigns. The concept was further refined through consultations and technical sessions with WP2 and WP4 to ensure alignment with interoperability and data-sharing requirements.

The use case has been validated with local DMOs and tourism SMEs, who confirmed its relevance for improving Andalusia’s tourism ecosystem and embedding sustainable criteria into their daily management and promotional activities.

The definition of Use Case 2 emerged from a thorough, collaborative process to address the Balearic Islands’ pressing sustainability challenges.

The process began with an internal need assessment led by regional tourism authorities, who identified a growing urgency to understand and manage the real-time effects of tourism on local infrastructure, natural resources, and residents’ quality of life. The Balearic Islands, as a highly seasonal and mature destination, face acute stress during peak periods, and there was a clear demand for timely, actionable data to support more agile and informed decision-making.

Following this, a feasibility analysis was carried out to determine which types of impact data could be reliably collected and integrated in real time. The assessment considered existing infrastructure, including mobility sensors, environmental monitoring stations, hotel booking engines, and visitor flow data from mobile devices and Wi-Fi hotspots. This technical groundwork confirmed that it was viable to aggregate and process multiple data streams to monitor tourism pressure as it evolves throughout the day or season.

Stakeholder involvement played a crucial role. We held targeted discussions with public authorities, local tourism boards, and key players in the tourism sector, including hotel associations and transport operators. These actors helped define not only the relevant indicators, such as occupancy rates, transport saturation, energy consumption, and visitor flows, but also the operational needs that the use case should support, such as adaptive crowd management or alerts for critical thresholds.

Document name:	D4.2 First quarterly report on DEPLOYTOUR pilot implementation	Page:	25 of 53
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU
		Version:	0.1
		Status:	Draft pending approval

This document translates some of the obligations from the grant agreement and in case of discrepancies, it is the grant agreement which prevails over this deliverable.

These exchanges informed the definition of priorities: the main goal identified was to support dynamic management of tourism flows, enabling institutions to anticipate saturation points and mitigate negative impacts in real time. This is particularly important in the Balearic context, where carrying capacity is limited, and public perception of overtourism is a growing concern. Another important aspect has been introduced, addressing not only the environment but also the social, economic, and territorial impacts.

Finally, the use case was refined through coordination with the technical work packages and validated to ensure compliance with the European Tourism Data Space principles. The result is a solid, stakeholder-driven use case that directly addresses the Balearic Islands' need for a more resilient, responsive tourism model, grounded in real-time data insights.

Table 8. KPI Total number of use cases identified (Pilot 1)

KPI 1: Total number of use cases identified	2
• Use cases in the phase: JUST HYPOTHESIS	0
• Use cases in the phase: ONGOING VALIDATION	0
• Use cases in the phase: COMPLETELY VALIDATED	2
• Use cases in the phase: ONBOARDING COMPLETED	0
• Use cases in the phase: DATA SHARING COMPLETED	0

Use case 1: Sustainability, Redistribution and Data-Driven Campaigns.

Needs addressed. Destinations require reliable data to align marketing strategies with sustainability goals and to redistribute tourist flows across time and territory. The use case addresses the need to integrate environmental and tourism indicators with marketing performance data, allowing destinations to reduce seasonality and pressure in over-visited areas while improving competitiveness.

Functional description. The use case describes a system for monitoring and guiding marketing actions based on sustainability and demand indicators. It integrates data from tourism statistics (INE, IECA, Eurostat), sustainability frameworks (TSI), PMS data, and digital marketing analytics (AdQuiver). By linking campaign metrics to sustainability KPIs such as density, intensity, and seasonality, the platform helps decision-makers adjust promotional efforts, target specific markets, and encourage travel during off-peak periods. The approach contributes to a more balanced and efficient management of tourism demand in line with ETDS standards.

Involved data providers. Turismo de Andalucía (EPGTDA), AdQuiver, IECA, INE, Oficina del Dato.

Data consumers. Regional and local DMOs, public authorities, and tourism businesses benefit from integrated sustainability and marketing insights.

Use Case 2: Sustainability Monitoring and Data Interoperability in the Balearic Islands

Needs addressed. Tourism destinations require a comprehensive system to measure sustainability performance (environmental, social, and economic dimensions) and facilitate access to reliable data. The use case addresses the need to integrate heterogeneous datasets from multiple institutions to support impact assessment, improve decision-making, and connect the Balearic Islands' regional data space with the European Tourism Data Space (ETDS).

Document name:	D4.2 First quarterly report on DEPLOYTOUR pilot implementation	Page:	26 of 53
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU
	Version:	0.1	Status: Draft pending approval

This document translates some of the obligations from the grant agreement and in case of discrepancies, it is the grant agreement which prevails over this deliverable.

Functional description. The use case develops an integrated sustainability monitoring framework combining official statistics (IBESTAT, INE, EUROSTAT), environmental data (MITECO, REE, energy and waste providers), and mobility information (AENA, EMT, TIB, Balearic Port Authority). Data are processed and visualised in dashboards to assess key indicators, including energy and water consumption, waste generation, land use, biodiversity, employment, and visitor mobility. The pilot validates how local data can be harmonised with ETDS standards using APIs and open formats (JSON-stat, CSV, shapefiles), enabling comparability and interoperability across regions.

Involved data providers: IBESTAT, INE, EUROSTAT, MITECO, REE, energy, water and waste data providers, AENA, EMT, TIB, Balearic Port Authority, Hotels and POIs, AVORIS, and the Balearic DMO.

Data consumers include the Balearic DMO, tourism and environmental authorities, data scientists, insight providers, and dashboard developers, who use the harmonised datasets for sustainability reporting and policy design.

3.2.3 Identification of data sources

The identification of data sources for **Use Case 1** builds on the existing data ecosystem managed by Turismo Andaluz’s Oficina del Dato, the regional department responsible for analysing and integrating tourism-related data in Andalucía. This office combines public and open datasets (e.g., official statistics, observatory data, sustainability indicators) with private data sources from industry partners, such as hotels and digital marketing platforms. In addition, the Oficina del Dato generates its own datasets, including satisfaction surveys from residents and visitors, offering a comprehensive perspective on tourism impacts.

For this use case, an ongoing data audit is being conducted to identify and evaluate the most relevant sources for inclusion in the pilot. This process ensures data interoperability and alignment with the European Tourism Data Space (ETDS) standards. The activity is carried out in close coordination with WP2 to guarantee technical compatibility, metadata harmonisation, and compliance with data-sharing protocols.

For Use Case 2, the identification and refinement of data sources followed a structured, iterative, and regionally informed process. This use case focuses on enabling mature destinations, specifically the Balearic Islands, to monitor the social, environmental, and economic impacts of tourism in near-real time, to support more responsive and sustainable destination management.

The process began with a functional assessment of the data needs required to implement Use Case 2. Regional stakeholders, including destination management organisations, public authorities, tourism professionals, and infrastructure managers, collaborated to define key indicators. These included metrics related to tourism pressure, resource consumption, local community well-being, environmental quality, and visitor satisfaction.

Following this initial scoping, an extensive inventory of data sources was created, drawing from regional, national, and European-level datasets. Each data source was reviewed in terms of:

- Thematic relevance to one or more impact dimensions
- Geographic and temporal granularity
- Update frequency and format
- Ownership and accessibility

A key success factor in this process has been the ongoing alignment with Work Package 2 (WP2), responsible for the technical architecture and data governance of the European

Document name:	D4.2 First quarterly report on DEPLOYTOUR pilot implementation	Page:	27 of 53
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU
	Version:	0.1	Status: Draft pending approval

This document translates some of the obligations from the grant agreement and in case of discrepancies, it is the grant agreement which prevails over this deliverable.

Tourism Data Space (ETDS). WP2 is supporting the technical review of each identified data source, with particular focus on:

- Technical availability, including APIs, structured datasets, and machine-readable formats
- Compliance with interoperability standards, particularly DCAT-AP
- Metadata quality and harmonisation requirements
- Feasibility for real-time or near real-time integration into ETDS infrastructures

This collaboration is still in progress and is allowing the team to assess not only the content relevance of each source but also its potential for onboarding and use in a shared data ecosystem.

In parallel, a refinement phase was launched. Datasets are iteratively reviewed and prioritised based on their strategic value, readiness, and ability to deliver timely insights. WP2 supports the development of integration pathways for sources that require reprocessing, transformation, or harmonisation. For sources with limited availability or low update frequency, alternative approaches or long-term onboarding plans are being considered.

The expected outcome of this joint effort is a validated, technically robust, and stakeholder-approved set of data sources that respond to the operational needs of Use Case 2. This process sets a solid foundation for implementation and serves as a scalable model for other destinations seeking to adopt real-time impact monitoring capabilities within the ETDS framework.

Table 9. KPI Total number of data providers identified (Pilot 2)

KPI 2: Total number of DATA PROVIDERS identified	12
• <i>Data providers in the phase: JUST HYPOTHESIS</i>	1
• <i>Data providers in the phase: ONGOING VALIDATION</i>	6
• <i>Data providers in the phase: COMPLETELY VALIDATED</i>	5
• <i>Data providers in the phase: ONBOARDING COMPLETED</i>	0
• <i>Data providers in the phase: DATA SHARING COMPLETED</i>	0

Project partners acting as data providers (4):

1. Turismo de Andalucía (EPGTDA) – Pilot 2 leader and main data aggregator. Provides the NAC tourism asset database and sustainability indicators, and manages the Oficina del Dato, which integrates regional open data, mobility, and environmental datasets.
2. AdQuiver – Partner providing digital marketing and behavioural campaign data.
3. Avoris – Partner providing Arrivals and overnight stays, divided by nationality, length of stay and season.
4. Anysolution and the University of the Balearic Islands – Partners aggregating the contributing regional tourism data and coordinating (Anysolution) the Balearic use case (UC2) as a result of the implementation of the Balearic Island Tourism DataSpace as a main data provider.

External / non-partner data providers (8):

5. Accommodation establishments (via Nexus PMS) – Data owners providing operational PMS data.
6. IECA (Andalusian Institute of Statistics and Cartography) – Regional statistical data.
7. INE (Spanish Statistical Office) – National tourism, economic, and labour statistics.
8. EUROSTAT – European-level harmonised statistical indicators.

Document name:	D4.2 First quarterly report on DEPLOYTOUR pilot implementation	Page:	28 of 53
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU
	Version:	0.1	Status: Draft pending approval

This document translates some of the obligations from the grant agreement and in case of discrepancies, it is the grant agreement which prevails over this deliverable.

9. IBESTAT (Balearic Islands Statistical Institute) – Regional data for tourism and sustainability.
10. MITECO (Spanish Ministry for Ecological Transition) – Environmental datasets (emissions, waste, water)
11. REE (Red Eléctrica de España) – National energy consumption and grid data
12. AENA / Balearic Port Authority / EMT / TIB – Mobility and transport data providers in the Balearic Islands.

Table 10. KPI Total number of datasets identified (Pilot 2)

KPI 3: Total number of DATASETS identified for sharing	42
• Datasets in the phase: JUST HYPOTHESIS	4
• Datasets in the phase: ONGOING VALIDATION	12
• Datasets in the phase: COMPLETELY VALIDATED	26
• Datasets in the phase: ONBOARDING COMPLETED	0
• Datasets in the phase: DATA SHARING COMPLETED	0

Of the total number of datasets identified, 13 refer to UC1, and 29 refer to UC2.

Table 11. KPI Total number of datasets of non-open data identified (Pilot 2)

KPI 4: Total number of DATASETS of NON-OPEN DATA identified for sharing	14
• Datasets in the phase: JUST HYPOTHESIS	0
• Datasets in the phase: ONGOING VALIDATION	13
• Datasets in the phase: COMPLETELY VALIDATED	1
• Datasets in the phase: ONBOARDING COMPLETED	0
• Datasets in the phase: DATA SHARING COMPLETED	0

Table 12. Data sources identified (Pilot 2)

Data source	Relative use cases	Usage	Accessibility (Open/Proprietary)
Adquiver Digital marketing platform data (Meta, Google ads, GA4, Adform)	1	Key metrics for marketing campaigns can indicate interest among target markets. These data will be generated once the DMO marketing campaigns in use case 1 are launched, and they will be used to monitor the campaign performance against the established KPIs (especially those that involve the sustainable indicators).	Proprietary (marketing campaign data coming from Andalucía DMO)
Hotel PMS through the Andalucía initiative NEXUS DATA PMS	1	Data from Andalusian hotels' Property Management Systems (PMS) will be used to understand visitor segments better and optimise marketing performance. The dataset includes information on bookings, occupancy rates, and pricing, enriched with demographic details such as guests' nationalities and origins. As this data is available in quasi-real time, it enables dynamic decision-making in marketing campaigns, allowing DMOs to allocate resources to channels with the most positive impact on key performance indicators (KPIs) and discontinue or adjust those	Proprietary owned by Andalucía DMO through the NEXUS DATA PMS initiative.

Document name:	D4.2 First quarterly report on DEPLOYTOUR pilot implementation	Page:	29 of 53
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU
	Version:	0.1	Status: Draft pending approval

This document translates some of the obligations from the grant agreement and in case of discrepancies, it is the grant agreement which prevails over this deliverable.

		that are not aligned with sustainability or profitability goals.	
INE (Spanish National Statistical Office)	1,2	Data from the Spanish National Statistical Office (INE) provides key statistical series relevant to tourism in the destinations participating in the pilot. Special emphasis is placed on economic and mobility datasets, including the series “Measurement of tourism flows using mobile phones.”, which measures tourist movements and flows based on anonymised mobile data. These datasets support the analysis of visitor behaviour, mobility patterns, and economic performance, offering a robust foundation for evaluating sustainability and competitiveness indicators in mature destinations.	Open
Instituto de Estadística y Cartografía de Andalucía	1	The Instituto de Estadística y Cartografía de Andalucía (IECA) is a public entity that provides official statistical and cartographic information for the Andalusian region. Its datasets support spatial and socio-economic analysis, offering valuable insights into tourism dynamics, land use, population distribution, and environmental indicators. These data are essential for contextualising tourism activity within broader territorial and sustainability frameworks and for integrating geographic and statistical perspectives in the analysis conducted through the pilot.	Open
COPERNICUS satellite data, European Environmental Agency	1,2	This georeferenced data enables characterization of the geographic areas where tourism activities can occur, accounting for their specific use cases and designations.	Open
NAC – Nexus Andalucía Connect	1	Provides insights into the geographical distribution of tourism supply, helping assess how marketing actions influence visitor flows and supporting decisions that foster spatially balanced and sustainable tourism development across Andalucía	Proprietary
IBESTAT, INE, EUROSTAT	UC2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Tourist expenditure data broken down by visitor, activity and region. · Arrivals and overnight stays, divided by nationality, length of stay and season. · Regional economic reports indicating the contribution of tourism. · Number of formal and informal jobs created in the tourism sector (hotels, guides, transport, etc.). · Proportion of revenue generated by large chains versus small local businesses. · Infrastructure projects and tourism services financed by public and private entities. · Data obtained from tourist surveys or consumption records. · Local environmental studies that measure pollution levels in tourist areas. · Biodiversity and monitoring of protected areas. 	Open

Document name:	D4.2 First quarterly report on DEPLOYTOUR pilot implementation	Page:	30 of 53
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU
	Version:	0.1	Status: Draft pending approval

This document translates some of the obligations from the grant agreement and in case of discrepancies, it is the grant agreement which prevails over this deliverable.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Statistics on energy sources used in the tourism sector. · Data on changes in land use, habitat loss or deforestation. · Surveys that include age, preferences, education, background, and behavior. · Surveys to assess how residents perceive tourism in terms of benefits and impacts. · Data on tourism jobs and businesses run by local residents. · Record of cultural events, traditions maintained, and restoration of historic sites. · Post-visit surveys to measure the visitor experience. · Information on wages, benefits, contracts and labor rights in tourism companies. · Number of training or awareness-raising training for tour operators and visitors. · Crime rates reported in tourist areas and access to emergency services. 	
--	--	---	--

3.2.4 Identification and involvement of stakeholders

Stakeholders were identified based on data relevance and ownership, decision-making influence, and technical capacity to contribute to the pilot’s data-sharing and sustainability objectives. The goal was to ensure a balanced representation of public authorities, private companies, and data intermediaries, consistent with the ETDS multi-actor governance model. Engagement activities included bilateral meetings, coordination sessions, and joint WP2–WP4 workshops (June–October 2025), focused on mapping data sources, defining governance models, and validating sustainability indicators. This process resulted in a validated map of 12 active data providers and 26 datasets, as well as the first version of a shared governance framework, which is currently being tested with WP2.

For Use Case 1 – Data-Driven Sustainable Marketing for Competitive and Resilient Destinations (Andalusia), the identification focused on stakeholders who can influence or benefit from integrating sustainability indicators into destination marketing and management. The Destination Management Organisation (DMO) plays a central role by integrating sustainability indicators into promotional strategies. At the same time, SMEs, hotels, and local authorities use these insights to optimise resource use, improve competitiveness, and enhance resilience.

Turismo de Andalucía (EPGTDA) leads the pilot, coordinating stakeholders through the NEXUS initiative, which connects the regional tourism ecosystem via data services, capacity building, and training. AdQuiver contributes adtech expertise and behavioural data; IECA, INE, and EUROSTAT provide reference statistical frameworks; and accommodation establishments (via Nexus PMS) contribute operational data in the Balearic Islands. IBESTAT, MITECO, AENA, and REE supply environmental and mobility datasets.

A communication and stakeholder involvement plan ensures all actors are informed, actively participate in the pilot, and receive practical guidance for future onboarding to the European Tourism Data Space (ETDS). The engagement process is being documented to support replication and knowledge transfer across other European destinations.

The success of Use Case 2 in the Balearic Islands relies heavily on the engagement and collaboration of a wide network of stakeholders from the tourism ecosystem. The following criteria guided the identification of stakeholders:

- Ownership or access to relevant tourism, mobility, sustainability, or environmental data

Document name:	D4.2 First quarterly report on DEPLOYTOUR pilot implementation	Page:	31 of 53
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU
	Version:	0.1	Status: Draft pending approval

- Operational responsibility in destination management or infrastructure
- Strategic relevance in policymaking, tourism governance, or data governance
- Technological capacity to contribute to or consume interoperable data services

Based on these criteria, a diverse set of stakeholders was mapped, including:

- Public authorities (Govern de les Illes Balears, IBESTAT, Consell de Mallorca, city councils)
- Tourism boards and DMOs
- Accommodation and transport providers (hotels, airport authority, public and private mobility operators)
- Environmental and infrastructure agencies (waste, water, energy)
- Academic and technical partners (University of the Balearic Islands – UIB, Anysolution)

The involvement process was carried out through a combination of:

- Three multi-stakeholder workshops, co-led by Anysolution and UIB, focused specifically on:
 - Mapping and validating existing and potential data sources
 - Exploring data sharing needs and barriers
 - Building consensus on the creation of a Balearic Islands Tourism Data Space, aligned with the European strategy of data convergence through the ETDS
- Bilateral interviews and technical meetings with data holders and consumers
- Working group sessions under WP6 to refine use case requirements and feasibility

These activities achieved key results:

- Consolidated a shared vision of tourism data collaboration in the region
- Identified both available data assets and current data gaps
- Secured preliminary commitments from several stakeholders to contribute data during implementation
- Raised awareness about technical and governance requirements under the ETDS

Among the key stakeholders whose continued support will be critical to the pilot’s success are:

- IBESTAT, for statistical and macroeconomic tourism data
- UIB, for methodological support and data modelling
- Govern de les Illes Balears (and public authorities), for governance leadership and data coordination
- Travel tech companies, hotels and mobility providers are primary sources of real-time visitor and flow data

Their current level of involvement includes active participation in workshops, providing data samples for analysis, and technical discussions on interoperability and access protocols. This ecosystem-based approach to stakeholder engagement strengthens the Balearic region's capacity not only to pilot the real-time impact monitoring use case but also to establish a long-term, interoperable tourism data infrastructure aligned with the ETDS.

Document name:	D4.2 First quarterly report on DEPLOYTOUR pilot implementation	Page:	32 of 53
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU
	Version:	0.1	Status: Draft pending approval

3.3 Pilot 3 - MICE sector support

The MICE (Meetings, Incentives, Conferences, and Exhibitions) sector is a key component of the tourism industry, driving year-round economic activity and supporting multiple industries. In Île-de-France, a region that relies heavily on business tourism, the DEPLOYTOUR project is implementing a pilot, led by EONA-X, to address key challenges and enhance the sector's competitiveness, resilience, and sustainability.

3.3.1 Definition of purpose

3.3.1.1 SMART Objectives

The SMART objective of this pilot is to support **three Île-de-France (IDF) stakeholders** in **diversifying their use of data products** to enable **better decision-making by spring 2027**.

The MICE sector in Île-de-France faces challenges limiting its potential:

- **A fragmented data ecosystem** prevents a complete view of business travellers' journeys, as each stakeholder holds partial information, making it difficult to optimise services and measure economic and environmental impacts.
- Destination Management Organisations (**DMOs**) **often lack comprehensive data** to understand business traveller behaviour and trends.
- **Absence of Real-Time Data Monitoring** for adapting strategies quickly.
- **Business travellers' demand hyper-personalised experiences**, including bleisure (combining business and leisure).
- **Growing pressure for sustainable event and travel options.**

This pilot explores several use cases to improve the MICE sector and support local stakeholders:

- **Holistic Sector Intelligence:** Providing clear and up-to-date insights into the size, trends, economic impact, and ecological footprint of the MICE sector.
- **Enhanced Visitor Understanding:** Gaining deeper knowledge of visitor behaviours, profiles, satisfaction levels, and journey patterns to better tailor services.
- **Efficient Decision-Making:** Using reliable, real-time data will support data-driven strategies and policy decisions.
- **Compliance with Event ISO Standards:** Leveraging data to help event organisers meet certification requirements.

By working closely with key stakeholders in the MICE sector and local actors, the pilot seeks to improve existing solutions thanks to data collaboration.

3.3.1.2 Involved partners, roles and responsibilities

Table 13. Involved partners (Pilot 3)

Partner	Value added to the pilot (tools, know-how, ...)	Role and expectations
Amadeus	Amadeus' expertise in the tourism and MICE sectors provides valuable insights into use cases and data product definitions.	Amadeus can provide relevant datasets for the use cases.
The Data Appeal Company	The Data Appeal Company shares its expertise in data intelligence for the tourism sector, leveraging AI-driven processes.	They are providing valuable datasets to support the identified use cases, such as data to monitor the destination

Document name:	D4.2 First quarterly report on DEPLOYTOUR pilot implementation	Page:	33 of 53	
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	
	Version:	0.1	Status:	Draft pending approval

This document translates some of the obligations from the grant agreement and in case of discrepancies, it is the grant agreement which prevails over this deliverable.

		status and outlook, its flows, type of visitors, foreseen events, expected expenditure, volume of visitors, sentiment, popularity, and the destination’s performance to improve the area’s overall sustainability for the MICE sector.
City Destinations Alliance (City DNA)	City Destinations Alliance’s network is an asset to speak to the Île-de-France region as well as to other European destinations.	CityDNA actively participates in workshops organised within the framework of Pilot 3.

3.3.2 Use case definition

The definition of Pilot 3’s use cases emerged from a structured, collaborative process combining stakeholder engagement, needs assessment, and iterative refinement.

In February 2025, the first in-person workshop brought together 15 organisations, including Amadeus, Choose Paris Region, Atout France, ICCA, Expo’stat, and Apidae, to identify sector challenges. Using a gamified approach, participants explored data spaces and their potential, and shared pain points where data collaboration could add value.

A second online workshop (March 2025) was organised to begin mapping stakeholder data products and identifying the data each holds or requires to implement solutions. An online questionnaire supplemented discussion, clarifying unaddressed details. By March, initial data products began taking shape.

Ongoing one-to-one meetings with key stakeholders deepened engagement, as clearly defined challenges made conversations more focused and actionable.

To expand reach, a webinar targeted UNIMEV members (France’s event professionals’ union) took place in May, while an October 2025 workshop with EMECA (European Major Exhibition Centres Association) addressed European venues.

These activities served dual purposes: educating stakeholders on data collaboration and the Common European Data Space’s benefits, while attracting new participants and demonstrating the pilot’s scalability. This iterative, stakeholder-driven approach ensured use cases aligned with real-world needs and feasibility.

Table 14. KPI Total number of use cases identified (Pilot 3)

KPI 1: Total number of use cases identified	3
• Use cases in the phase: <i>JUST HYPOTHESIS</i>	0
• Use cases in the phase: <i>ONGOING VALIDATION</i>	3
• Use cases in the phase: <i>COMPLETELY VALIDATED</i>	0
• Use cases in the phase: <i>ONBOARDING COMPLETED</i>	0
• Use cases in the phase: <i>DATA SHARING COMPLETED</i>	0

Important note: The following use cases are currently under development and will be refined based on feedback from upcoming meetings with data consumers. Please note that some use cases, particularly those involving public institutions, may be subject to changes or removal depending on the political context.

Document name:	D4.2 First quarterly report on DEPLOYTOUR pilot implementation	Page:	34 of 53
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU
	Version:	0.1	Status: Draft pending approval

This document translates some of the obligations from the grant agreement and in case of discrepancies, it is the grant agreement which prevails over this deliverable.

Use Case 1: Data on Seminars and Business Events in Hotel Structures

Needs Addressed. Enhancing the understanding of professional events, such as congresses, business meetings, and seminars, hosted in hotel structures across Île-de-France.

Objective. Integrate multi-source data from hotels and partners to create a unified, reliable dataset.

Functional Description. Enable Atout France to access:

- **Number of business travellers** (distinguishing between "classic" business trips and event attendees).
- **Occupancy rates** of MICE spaces (seminars, conferences, trade fairs).
- **Annual event statistics:** Number of events, total event days, and average participants per event.
- **Geographical origin** of participants (country-level breakdown).
- **Seasonality trends** in MICE activity.
- **Bleisure trends:** Share of travellers extending stays for leisure purposes.

Data Consumers. Atout France

Data Providers (to be confirmed). Hotels' occupancy and prices (saturation level and prices, according to OTA channels), expected attendance, impacts and spending on event locations/areas, a data pack containing the registry of points of interest within a defined area - The Data Appeal Company

Use Case 2: Tourism and Business Traveller Observation in Île-de-France

Needs Addressed. Supporting Choose Paris Region for tourism observation, particularly in the MICE sector, to obtain high-quality information from a wider range of suppliers.

Objective.

- Conduct an annual study collecting aeroplane, train, and road travel data via a service provider (selected through a call for tender).
- Ingest multi-source data, including contributions from EONA-X, to produce robust statistics.
- Support regional stakeholders in monitoring tourism trends and informing policy decisions.

Functional Description. Enable Choose Paris Region (or the survey company) to:

- **Measure tourist flows:** Number of stays, nights, and tourist consumption (expenditure during visits).
- **Estimate nationality distribution** in terms of attendance and spending.
- **Create tourist profiles:** Reasons for stays, sociodemographic characteristics, and destination familiarity.
- **Analyse traveller practices:** Length of stay, accommodation types, leisure activities, and multi-destination trips.
- **Assess satisfaction:** Reasons for satisfaction/dissatisfaction, likelihood to recommend, and return intentions.

Data Consumers. Choose Paris Region (or the survey company)

Document name:	D4.2 First quarterly report on DEPLOYTOUR pilot implementation	Page:	35 of 53
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU
	Version:	0.1	Status: Draft pending approval

This document translates some of the obligations from the grant agreement and in case of discrepancies, it is the grant agreement which prevails over this deliverable.

Data Providers. Train operators (SCNF), airlines and airport (ADP), bus companies, payment providers

Use Case 3: Compliance with Event ISO Standards

Needs Addressed. Facilitate compliance with ISO event standards by leveraging data-driven certification for event organisers. EXPO’STAT, a leader in event auditing (with 650+ events audited annually), seeks to enhance data verification processes and securely share certificates via the DEPLOYTOUR data space.

Objective.

- Support EXPO’STAT in enriching data sources to simplify audits, ensuring impartiality, confidentiality, and independence.
- Enable secure, sovereign exposure of client certificates to authorized stakeholders via the EONA-X data space.

Functional Description.

- Connect to the EONA-X catalog to feed verification systems with reliable indicators.
- Expose certificates securely to selected partners via the data space.
- Provide aggregated data (e.g., event attendance trends, compliance metrics) to support industry benchmarking.

Data Consumers. EXPO’STAT (to consume data from third parties)

Data Providers. EXPO’STAT (to expose certificates via a data space), identified stakeholders

3.3.3 Identification of data sources

Once the challenges and data consumers were identified, we invited data consumers to create their “data wish list”, outlining the ideal datasets they would like to access if all possibilities were available.

EONA-X is now engaging with DEPLOYTOUR partners, such as Amadeus and The Data Appeal Company, as well as external stakeholders, to assess which data they can provide and under what conditions.

It is important to note that data providers and consumers are the ones negotiating the terms and conditions for exchanging these identified data products, which is why this process may take some time.

Table 15. KPI Total number of data providers identified (Pilot 3)

KPI 2: Total number of DATA PROVIDERS identified	3
• Data providers in the phase: JUST HYPOTHESIS	1
• Data providers in the phase: ONGOING VALIDATION	2
• Data providers in the phase: COMPLETELY VALIDATED	0
• Data providers in the phase: ONBOARDING COMPLETED	0
• Data providers in the phase: DATA SHARING COMPLETED	0

Table 16. KPI Total number of datasets identified (Pilot 3)

KPI 3: Total number of DATASETS identified for sharing	3
• Datasets in the phase: JUST HYPOTHESIS	1
• Datasets in the phase: ONGOING VALIDATION	2

Document name:	D4.2 First quarterly report on DEPLOYTOUR pilot implementation	Page:	36 of 53
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU
	Version:	0.1	Status: Draft pending approval

• Datasets in the phase: COMPLETELY VALIDATED	0
• Datasets in the phase: ONBOARDING COMPLETED	0
• Datasets in the phase: DATA SHARING COMPLETED	0

Table 17. KPI Total number of datasets of non-open data identified (Pilot 3)

KPI 4: Total number of DATASETS of NON-OPEN DATA identified for sharing	3
• Datasets in the phase: JUST HYPOTHESIS	1
• Datasets in the phase: ONGOING VALIDATION	2
• Datasets in the phase: COMPLETELY VALIDATED	0
• Datasets in the phase: ONBOARDING COMPLETED	0
• Datasets in the phase: DATA SHARING COMPLETED	0

Table 18. Data sources identified (Pilot 3)

Data source	Relative use cases	Usage	Accessibility (Open/Proprietary)
The Data Appeal Company	1, 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Predicted attendance and spending on events' locations and areas Number of events organised per year Events Impact Hotel occupancy levels and prices (OTA channels) POIs Registry regarding a specific area 	Proprietary
SNCF	2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Arrival and departure of business travellers in Île-de-France by train Timetables Capacity Disruption information 	Proprietary
Expo'stat	3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Event certificates Event attendance trends Compliance metrics 	Proprietary

3.3.4 Identification and involvement of stakeholders

The stakeholder identification and engagement process for the DEPLOYTOUR MICE pilot followed a structured, iterative approach that combined targeted outreach, collaborative workshops, and direct interviews to ensure comprehensive stakeholder engagement. Stakeholders were selected based on their roles within the MICE ecosystem (e.g., DMOs, event organisers, tourism boards, venue operators).

Document name:	D4.2 First quarterly report on DEPLOYTOUR pilot implementation	Page:	37 of 53
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU
	Version:	0.1	Status: Draft pending approval

This document translates some of the obligations from the grant agreement and in case of discrepancies, it is the grant agreement which prevails over this deliverable.

As for the activities carried out, here is the roadmap:

- December 2024 – BEFuture Event, another European project. EONA-X was invited to participate in explaining this pilot. This event was a great opportunity to meet with the local ecosystem, including Choose Paris Region, SITE France, Atout France, Vi Paris, and UNIMEV.
- January 2025 – A few online introductory sessions were held to present DEPLOYTOUR, the data space concepts of the pilot.
- February 2025 – In-person workshop with a gamified approach to explain data space concepts, interactive session to define key pain points in the MICE sector collectively.
- March 2025 – Online data mapping workshop
- May 2025 – Webinar for event organisers in partnership with UNIMEV (French Union of Event Professions), to continue onboarding new stakeholders and gather input on practical data needs.
- From June 2025 – One-to-one Interviews: Conducted individual interviews with stakeholders to map existing services and data assets, determine preferred levels of involvement, validate use cases and confirm stakeholder roles (as data consumers/providers).

Each time we met with a stakeholder, we asked which other entity to contact, enabling us to define a comprehensive MICE actors map.

Additional request: Asked stakeholders to identify other relevant actors to involve in the pilot. This multi-phase approach is ensuring that the pilot’s development is stakeholder-driven and aligned with sector needs.

As key stakeholders, we can mention:

Atout France: data consumer (public entity) in use case 1

Choose Paris Region: data consumer (public entity) in use case 2

Expo’stat: data consumer (private and SME entity) and data provider (private and SME entity) in use case 3

The Data Appeal Company: data provider (DEPLOYTOUR partner) in use cases 1 and 2

UNIMEV (French Union of Event Professions) is a valuable support for promoting data-sharing initiatives and the MICE pilot within its network. Moreover, as part of their “Contrat de filière”, they mention DEPLOYTOUR in action 29: “Identify tools or means for sharing best practices and data with a view to improving the quality of participants' journeys and experiences (stays) in the host region.” They are a valuable support in promoting data-sharing initiatives and the MICE pilot within their network. This contract, structured around five priority areas, constitutes a roadmap for the next five years. It aims to strengthen the role of events as a lever for influence and regional dynamism; position France as an international leader in events; promote the sector’s CSR commitment; exploit data for a personalised and effective marketing strategy; and accelerate innovation with a particular focus on AI and new sustainable practices.

ICCA (International Congress and Convention Association) is a valuable partner in promoting data-sharing initiatives and the MICE pilot within its network.

EMECA - European Major Exhibition Centres Association: they are a valuable support in promoting data sharing initiatives, and the MICE pilot among their network

Document name:	D4.2 First quarterly report on DEPLOYTOUR pilot implementation	Page:	38 of 53
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU
	Version:	0.1	Status: Draft pending approval

This document translates some of the obligations from the grant agreement and in case of discrepancies, it is the grant agreement which prevails over this deliverable.

3.4 Pilot 4 - Leveraging cultural heritage to diversify tourism offer: the case of Ano Syros (Greece)

3.4.1 Definition of purpose

3.4.1.1 SMART Objectives

The key focus of Pilot 4 is to support the transition of an established, high-traffic summer tourism model into a more sustainable and resilient cultural heritage destination.

The medieval settlement of Ano Syros serves as a representative case study, combining a rich cultural heritage with significant physical constraints related to accessibility and pronounced seasonal fluctuations in visitor numbers between summer and winter.

The design of the pilot's objectives follows a transferable and scalable approach that can be applied to heritage sites with similar characteristics across Europe. It is structured around three strategic pillars:

- **Development of engaging cultural tourist experiences:** a main aspect of the purpose of Pilot 4 is to harness key characteristic attributes of the heritage site and its architecture, which can highlight Ano Syros as a unique cultural destination. The key ambition of Pilot 4 is to capitalise on the site's distinctive attributes and architectural fabric to enhance the cultural tourism offer and promote Ano Syros as a unique heritage destination of regional and European significance.
- **Enhancement of accessibility and preservation of the cultural heritage assets of Ano Syros:** The pilot aims to refine the existing tourism model by prioritising restoration interventions on built heritage and by introducing alternative solutions to improve accessibility, particularly for visitor groups with physical limitations.
- **Creation of compelling narratives to redefine the destination's image:** Through storytelling and narrative-based visitor experiences, the pilot seeks to diversify the tourism offer, strengthen cultural identity, and foster year-round engagement with the site.

3.4.1.2 Involved partners, roles and responsibilities

Table 19. Involved partners (Pilot 4)

Partner	Value added to the pilot (tools, know-how, ...)	Role and expectations
PLEIADES	Pleiades holds a dual role, encompassing both managerial and technical responsibilities: Managerial: Coordinating the various partners involved in this pilot and ensuring alignment of the pilot's activities and outcomes with the overall objectives of the other Work Packages (WPs). Technical: Providing 3D data and developing the application or web platform through which end users will interact with the pilot's outputs.	Pilot's Coordinator
The Data Appeal Company	Data sharing and provision: Supply tourism-related data and information on Points of Interest (POIs) and	Partner

Document name:	D4.2 First quarterly report on DEPLOYTOUR pilot implementation	Page:	39 of 53	
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	
	Version:	0.1	Status:	Draft pending approval

This document translates some of the obligations from the grant agreement and in case of discrepancies, it is the grant agreement which prevails over this deliverable.

	<p>destinations, both at the individual POI level and in aggregated form.</p> <p>Support and training: Deliver dedicated support and training sessions for Destination Management Organisations (DMOs) and project partners to facilitate effective data use and integration.</p> <p>Performance monitoring: Provide Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), data packs, and related services to evaluate destination performance over time, ensuring indicators and tools are continuously adapted to partners' needs and expectations.</p>	
UNISYSTEMS	<p>Contribute to the definition of a use case.</p> <p>Identify and provide relevant data sources (e.g., tourist flows, climate data, local narratives).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Contribute to the definition of standards and metadata models to ensure data interoperability. · Provide content and develop digital storytelling components. · Liaise with local data providers and stakeholders for data collection and validation. · Organise workshops with local stakeholders to support co-creation and dissemination activities. 	Partner
EUROPEANA	<p>Develop and integrate storytelling elements that enhance user engagement and interpretation.</p> <p>Coordinate stakeholder engagement activities to ensure co-creation, validation, and dissemination of outcomes.</p> <p>Facilitate collaboration among local actors, data providers, and cultural organisations.</p>	Partner
ARCTUR	<p>Contribution to discussions on standards, metadata and interoperability for 3D and immersive cultural heritage content.</p> <p>Advisory support on digital storytelling and experience design for cultural tourism. Participation as a data</p>	Partner

Document name:	D4.2 First quarterly report on DEPLOYTOUR pilot implementation	Page:	40 of 53
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU
	Version:	0.1	Status: Draft pending approval

	consumer in Use Case 2 (“Digital Cultural Route”), by accessing and using selected datasets made available through the Tourism Data Space to explore and demonstrate innovative visitor experiences (i.e., AR/XR with 3D models).	
CITY DESTINATIONS ALLIANCE	Knowledge sharing and best practices Accessibility initiative consulting on sustainability, trends, and visitor experience.	Partner
EONA-X	Expertise in data space ecosystems Can allow access to data sources, support data exchanges and provide data products. Experience in implementing use cases	Partner

3.4.2 Use case definition

The development of the proposed use cases was guided by the main pillars of the Pilot’s objective and aimed at engaging a diverse range of end users. It was essential to design use cases that address the needs of key stakeholders across multiple sectors, including public administration officials, heritage representatives, and business and tourism operators, who can provide critical feedback on the development and deployment of sustainable methodological practices in tourist destinations.

The ideation phase

During this phase, the feasibility attributes of each use case were explored through brief consultations with representatives of the selected stakeholder groups, with discussions tailored to each use case’s specific requirements. The subsequent prioritisation process considered factors such as long-term sustainability, potential for innovation in regional heritage promotion, and opportunities to regulate visitor flows during peak tourist periods.

The final selection comprises three (3) Use Cases, each promoting distinct applications of cultural heritage to support sustainable tourism management. These use cases are designed to support diverse business models while enhancing the visitor experience.

Table 20. KPI Total number of use cases identified (Pilot 4)

KPI 1: Total number of use cases identified	3
• Use cases in the phase: <i>JUST HYPOTHESIS</i>	0
• Use cases in the phase: <i>ONGOING VALIDATION</i>	2
• Use cases in the phase: <i>COMPLETELY VALIDATED</i>	1
• Use cases in the phase: <i>ONBOARDING COMPLETED</i>	0
• Use cases in the phase: <i>DATA SHARING COMPLETED</i>	0

Document name:	D4.2 First quarterly report on DEPLOYTOUR pilot implementation	Page:	41 of 53
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU
	Version:	0.1	Status: Draft pending approval

This document translates some of the obligations from the grant agreement and in case of discrepancies, it is the grant agreement which prevails over this deliverable.

Use Case 1: Data-Driven Cultural Heritage Preservation for Sustainable Tourism Planning

Needs addressed. Use Case 1 aims to implement a data-driven methodology to support the prioritisation of restoration needs for built heritage. The use case promotes a sustainable approach to selecting and repurposing buildings for long-term tourism applications, ensuring their preservation while enhancing local tourism development.

Functional description. The proposed outcome is an accessible **Web Portal** designed to centralize and manage the data required for complex prioritization of restoration interventions. The portal integrates a **GIS database** containing geo-tagged records of all documented buildings in Ano Syros, alongside an embedded **dashboard** to support evidence-based decision-making for the relevant authorities. Use Case 1 operates under a **Business-to-Government (B2G)** model.

Involved data providers. 5DARCHAID project, The Data Appeal Company, EUROPEANA

Data Consumers. Local municipality officials, regional technical department authorities, real-estate representatives.

Use case 2: Enhanced Cultural Route Mapping

Needs addressed. Use Case 2 focuses on the development of a heritage-oriented cultural route map designed to showcase the regional cultural identity, enhance visitor engagement, and address accessibility challenges for physical visitation.

Functional description. The use case creates a **digital, immersive route** of Ano Syros' Medieval Settlement, highlighting both tangible and intangible heritage. The design also incorporates VR and MR experiences so as visitors—including those with physical limitations—can explore hidden alleys and Points of Interest through an online platform with rich multimedia and historical content. This approach diversifies the visitor experience, overcomes accessibility challenges, and offers interactive ways to engage with the site's cultural and architectural treasures.

Involved data providers. 5DARCHAID project, The Data Appeal Company, EUROPEANA (different owners such as: Hellenic Literary and Historical Archive, National Research Foundation Eleftherios Venizelos, Academy of Athens, Institute of Historical Research) Syros Agenda, Openweather map

Data Consumers. Local municipality officials, Museums, Cultural organizations (such as research institutes, local museums, heritage NGOs, and university departments)

Use case 3: Gamified Tour Experience

Needs addressed. Use Case 3 introduces a gamified approach to exploring the heritage site of Ano Syros, engaging both visitors and cultural stakeholders as active participants and points of interest (POIs). The use case also aims to mitigate congestion in high-traffic areas by guiding visitors along alternative routes.

Functional description. This use case develops a **web application** featuring a gamified user interface with optimisation options tailored for the end user. The embedded gamified storytelling will highlight key cultural landmarks while promoting local small and medium-sized

Document name:	D4.2 First quarterly report on DEPLOYTOUR pilot implementation	Page:	42 of 53
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU
	Version:	0.1	Status: Draft pending approval

This document translates some of the obligations from the grant agreement and in case of discrepancies, it is the grant agreement which prevails over this deliverable.

enterprises (SMEs), such as traditional workshops and tourist-oriented businesses, thereby enhancing both cultural and economic engagement.

Involved data providers: 5DARCHAID project, The Data Appeal Company, EUROPEANA (different owners such as: Hellenic Literary and Historical Archive, National Research Foundation Eleftherios Venizelos, Academy of Athens, Institute of Historical Research) & Syros Agenda.

Data Consumers: Game design entities, cultural organisations, SMEs

3.4.3 Identification of data sources

The design of the use cases identified a set of essential data sources critical for the deployment and added value of each application. Priority was given to datasets that provide a comprehensive representation of Ano Syros as a dynamic tourist destination, including documentation of tangible and intangible built heritage, architectural and archival records, and building-condition data to support safe planning.

Key datasets also include tourism POIs, events, and regional weather and climate variables to support optimised visitation planning. 3D datasets and 360° digital walkthroughs, along with heatmaps of visitor density, were incorporated to enhance immersive experiences, support route planning, and mitigate congestion.

The feasibility of acquiring the datasets and their relevance were validated through stakeholder consultations, resulting in a prioritised dataset list, with lower-priority items, such as boat schedules, excluded. This process was carried out in close alignment with WP2 objectives.

Table 21. KPI Total number of data providers identified (Pilot 4)

KPI 2: Total number of DATA PROVIDERS identified	5
• <i>Data providers in the phase: JUST HYPOTHESIS</i>	0
• <i>Data providers in the phase: ONGOING VALIDATION</i>	5
• <i>Data providers in the phase: COMPLETELY VALIDATED</i>	0
• <i>Data providers in the phase: ONBOARDING COMPLETED</i>	0
• <i>Data providers in the phase: DATA SHARING COMPLETED</i>	0

Table 22. KPI Total number of datasets identified (Pilot 4)

KPI 3: Total number of DATASETS identified for sharing	10
• <i>Datasets in the phase: JUST HYPOTHESIS</i>	1
• <i>Datasets in the phase: ONGOING VALIDATION</i>	9
• <i>Datasets in the phase: COMPLETELY VALIDATED</i>	0
• <i>Datasets in the phase: ONBOARDING COMPLETED</i>	0
• <i>Datasets in the phase: DATA SHARING COMPLETED</i>	0

Table 23. KPI Total number of datasets of non-open data identified (Pilot 4)

KPI 4: Total number of DATASETS of NON-OPEN DATA identified for sharing	4
• <i>Datasets in the phase: JUST HYPOTHESIS</i>	1
• <i>Datasets in the phase: ONGOING VALIDATION</i>	2
• <i>Datasets in the phase: COMPLETELY VALIDATED</i>	1
• <i>Datasets in the phase: ONBOARDING COMPLETED</i>	0
• <i>Datasets in the phase: DATA SHARING COMPLETED</i>	0

Document name:	D4.2 First quarterly report on DEPLOYTOUR pilot implementation	Page:	43 of 53
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU
	Version:	0.1	Status: Draft pending approval

This document translates some of the obligations from the grant agreement and in case of discrepancies, it is the grant agreement which prevails over this deliverable.

Table 24. Data sources identified (Pilot 4)

Data source	Relative use cases	Usage	Accessibility (Open/Proprietary)
3D Photorealistic Model of the entire Settlement of Ano Syros (PLEIADES)	UC1, UC2, UC3	Provides detailed geometric and spatial data on the built heritage of the Ano Syros settlement. The digital twin enables virtual tours and enhances digital storytelling. It supports tourism promotion, preservation efforts, and data-driven urban planning. For ETDS, it provides a template for integrating high-quality visualisations of cultural destinations.	Open
Buildings' 3D Data Models (PLEIADES)	UC1, UC2, UC3	Detailed geometric and spatial 3D models of historical buildings, allowing advanced analysis of architectural heritage, aiding in conservation, restoration planning, and virtual exploration. In ETDS, this dataset promotes sustainable tourism by combining cultural heritage with immersive technologies.	Open
Buildings' Pathology Data (PLEIADES)	UC1, UC2, UC3	Provides an extensive geographic visualisation of the condition of Ano Syros, structural defects, architectural alterations, and its historical background. Each building entry is georeferenced and includes information on materials, architectural typology & value, pathology, and the extent and significance of preservation. This data product offering can support targeted investments and/or the prioritisation of interventions related to the sustainable exploitation of the tourist destination and visitor safety. For ETDS, it can provide insight into tourism investment opportunities and cultural tourism promotion.	Open
Route Network of the entire settlement of	UC1, UC2, UC3	Provides the digital route network of Ano Syros and georeferenced 360° spheres, pedestrian routes, and pathways of the Ano Syros	Open

Document name:	D4.2 First quarterly report on DEPLOYTOUR pilot implementation	Page:	44 of 53
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU
		Version:	0.1
		Status:	Draft pending approval

This document translates some of the obligations from the grant agreement and in case of discrepancies, it is the grant agreement which prevails over this deliverable.

Ano Syros (PLEIADES)		Settlement, and supports flexible navigation and route planning for AR/VR applications and accessibility assessments, and helps create personalised itineraries for ETDS users.	
Weather data & weather forecasts (2 possible providers: https://openweathermap.org/api OR The Data Appeal Company)	UC2, UC3	Aggregates live data on real-time weather conditions for the island of Syros, including alerts for extreme weather and forecasts, to help assess how weather and climate influence tourism traffic patterns, seasonal logistics, and destination resilience. This is vital for creating climate-adaptive tourism strategies and promoting sustainable practices.	Proprietary
Human Mapping Data (The Data Appeal Company)	UC2, UC3	Human Mapping data provide visitor occupancy, visitor flow, visitor capacity, and dispersion measures to inform the deployment of sustainable visitor management policies.	Proprietary
Europeana Digital Cultural objects: Historical photographs of the island of Syros (Europeana)	UC2, UC3	Provides historical context to promote historical tourism experiences; digital applications, such as rephotography, that show the impact of tourism and human intervention on the landscape; and the cultural heritage of Ano Syros.	CC BY, Open
Europeana Digital Cultural objects: Textual cards related to Syros (Europeana)	UC2, UC3	Provides archival data and historical context to support cultural tourism applications that promote Ano Syros as a heritage destination.	CC BY -NC-SA, Open
Europeana Digital Cultural objects: Photographs and portraits related to Syros (Europeana)	UC2, UC3	Provides digital cultural heritage content to support cultural tourism, highlighting the site's tangible and intangible aspects.	InC, Proprietary
Europeana Digital Cultural objects: Vintage photographs of Syros (Europeana)	UC2, UC3	This dataset aggregates digital archival content to promote heritage-driven tourism experiences and showcase Ano Syros as a cultural destination.	CC BY-NC, Open

Document name:	D4.2 First quarterly report on DEPLOYTOUR pilot implementation	Page:	45 of 53
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU
		Version:	0.1
		Status:	Draft pending approval

This document translates some of the obligations from the grant agreement and in case of discrepancies, it is the grant agreement which prevails over this deliverable.

Europeana Digital Cultural objects: General objects about Syros (Europeana)	UC2, UC3	Aggregates digital cultural heritage objects to provide historical context and support cultural tourism practices, highlighting the site's tangible and intangible aspects.	Mixed licenses
Tourism POI data (The Data Appeal Company)	UC1, UC2, UC3	This data pack provides a registry of points of interest on Ano Syros, including categories related to tourism such as hospitality, food and beverage, attractions, and transportation. It supports price-range classification, destination competitiveness analysis, and the development of tourism strategies.	Proprietary
OTA saturation and prices datapack: Hotel Prices and occupancy rates (The Data Appeal Company)	UC1, UC2, UC3	Provides coverage data in terms of the number of offers, price levels, and occupancy rates for hospitality-related POIs. This enables a more strategic assessment of OTA intermediation and market dynamics in a given area.	Proprietary
Event & Festival Data (Open Syros Agenda)	PL.04.02 PL.04.03	The live mapping of local Cultural Events & Festivals and data, including Name of events, Date, Location and time, festival, performance and screenings mapping, to support targeted cultural tourism strategies and route planning for visitors, to extend tourism seasonality.	Open

3.4.4 Identification and involvement of stakeholders

The stakeholder selection process focused on organisations and authorities active in regional tourism and cultural heritage, engaging them as potential end users to co-design the three use cases. Engagement focused on public and private sector representatives capable of supporting long-term cultural tourism initiatives. Stakeholders were categorised into three groups: Local Municipality Representatives, Cultural Organisations, and Tourism-Oriented SMEs.

The onboarding process began with participation in local events, followed by one-to-one meetings to evaluate potential involvement. Selection criteria included relevance to each use case, policy influence, expertise in community engagement, and prior innovative work.

Local Municipality Representatives are essential for project feasibility and policy guidance and serve as end users, particularly for Use Case 1, as they will be the key implementers of ETDS for strategic intervention planning on built heritage. Selected officials from the Technical, City Planning, Culture, and Tourism departments supported Use Cases 1 and 2 by providing insights on interventions, regulatory requirements, and sustainable tourism strategies.

Document name:	D4.2 First quarterly report on DEPLOYTOUR pilot implementation	Page:	46 of 53
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU
	Version:	0.1	Status: Draft pending approval

This document translates some of the obligations from the grant agreement and in case of discrepancies, it is the grant agreement which prevails over this deliverable.

Cultural Organisation, including research institutes, local museums, heritage NGOs, and university departments. Regional cultural representatives and heritage stakeholders support the development of best practices to promote tangible and intangible heritage. They provide expertise on regional cultural identity, constraints, and best practices to engage visitors within a more sustainable tourism model. They are involved in Use Cases 2 and 3 as immediate stakeholders.

Tourism SMEs and local tourism representatives are engaged in Use Cases 2 and 3 to contribute to defining data sources and developing end-user applications actively. Priority is given to businesses operating within the historical settlement and to SMEs providing design services for tourists.

Through workshops, meetings, and targeted consultations, stakeholders validate pilot objectives, refine methodologies, and ensure alignment with local cultural and tourism strategies. Their continued involvement is essential for successful implementation and long-term sustainability.

3.5 Pilot 5 – Empowering SMEs in Tourism through a Collaborative TravelTech

Tourism is a key driver of Lapland’s economy, with SMEs forming the backbone of the sector. Yet many of them face increasing pressure to operate efficiently and make informed, data-driven decisions. Within the DEPLOYTOUR project, Pilot 5 – Empowering SMEs – aims to address these challenges by demonstrating how the European Tourism Data Space, together with regional data and TravelTech actors, can enhance SME competitiveness, resilience, and sustainable year-round growth through improved access to shared tourism data.

3.5.1 Definition of purpose

3.5.1.1 SMART Objectives

Pilot 5 – Empowering SMEs – addresses the challenges faced by tourism SMEs in Lapland: fragmented data, limited resources, and insufficient expertise to leverage data spaces effectively. The pilot aims to demonstrate how data spaces can empower SMEs to make data-driven decisions, enhance competitiveness, and foster sustainable, year-round growth in tourism by 2027.

Tourism SMEs often struggle to collect, process, and interpret data, and the fragmented tourism data landscape limits access to comprehensive market insights. The pilot demonstrates how data spaces can simplify data access and utilisation and support the development of a collaborative ecosystem that connects SMEs with TravelTech and data actors, offering user-friendly, industry-specific solutions.

To demonstrate this in practice, the pilot develops one use case:

- Marketing Assistant – enabling SMEs to plan, test, and evaluate data-driven campaigns that support year-round tourism.

3.5.1.2 Involved partners, roles and responsibilities

Table 25. Involved partners (Pilot 5)

Partner	Value added to the pilot (tools, know-how, ...)	Role and expectations
---------	---	-----------------------

Document name:	D4.2 First quarterly report on DEPLOYTOUR pilot implementation	Page:	47 of 53
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU
	Version:	0.1	Status: Draft pending approval

Lapland UAS	Deep knowledge of the context and expertise, coordination capabilities.	Pilot's coordinator
AnySolution	<p>Technical expertise and activities to prepare SMEs to participate in the Tourism Data Space.</p> <p>Understanding the benefits of Data Value and Data Space.</p> <p>DataSpace Onboarding Guidelines for data consumption.</p>	<p>Support in the identification of data-driven strategy value, needs and requirements of SMEs.</p> <p>Support in training.</p> <p>Requirements to connect to the DS as a consumer.</p> <p>Requirements to connect as a provider. Data catalogues creation. Governance compliance.</p>
NECSTouR	Technical expertise, support in the development of the ecosystem and needed data solutions through the Tourism of Tomorrow Lab.	Help build the required pilot ecosystem by gathering requirements and needs from participating SMEs. Transforming the functional needs into technical requirements. Support in the implementation of the data solutions.
The Data Appeal Company	An expert in data intelligence for the tourism sector and AI processes.	Provision of KPIs/Datapacks for evaluating the Destination's qualitative performance over time; KPIs, Datapacks, and services will be adjusted to partners' needs and expectations.
City DNA	Community and network: a network of European DMOs.	Scalability of the Pilot and its processes for identifying the needs and requirements of DMOs and SMEs, and for accessing a broad range of DMO data and how they use it.
Eona-X	<p>Expertise in data space ecosystems</p> <p>Access to data sources</p> <p>Experience in use cases</p>	<p>Sparring and collaboration in developing use cases and stakeholder engagement</p> <p>Data space partner.</p> <p>Supporting data exchanges.</p> <p>Providing data products</p>

Document name:	D4.2 First quarterly report on DEPLOYTOUR pilot implementation	Page:	48 of 53
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU
Version:	0.1	Status:	Draft pending approval

This document translates some of the obligations from the grant agreement and in case of discrepancies, it is the grant agreement which prevails over this deliverable.

3.5.2 Use case definition

The pilot adopted a structured, needs-based, and iterative process to define its use cases. It began with discussions with Visit Levi, the regional DMO, to identify data-related challenges and SME requirements. Between March and May 2025, diverse stakeholders—including tourism SMEs, local TravelTech and data companies, the DMO, and the municipality—were interviewed to assess needs, readiness, and interest in joining the ETDS. The findings were analysed and grouped into potential use cases addressing concrete SME challenges through data-driven solutions.

A co-creation workshop in Levi on 22 May 2025 refined and prioritised these use cases based on stakeholder feedback. The final selection was agreed with the DMO according to feasibility and SME relevance. Continuous one-to-one meetings during the spring, summer and fall of 2025 and a major regional event on 9 October, engaging over 130 companies, fostered discussion, collaboration, ecosystem building, and scalability. This iterative, stakeholder-driven process ensured that the selected use case reflected real SME needs and supported socio-technical innovation, data readiness, and long-term collaboration.

Table 26. KPI Total number of use cases identified (Pilot 5)

KPI 1: Total number of use cases identified	1
• Use cases in the phase: JUST HYPOTHESIS	0
• Use cases in the phase: ONGOING VALIDATION	1
• Use cases in the phase: COMPLETELY VALIDATED	0
• Use cases in the phase: ONBOARDING COMPLETED	0
• Use cases in the phase: DATA SHARING COMPLETED	0

Seasonal fluctuations are too extreme in many tourism regions in Lapland, weakening local economic resilience, year-round employment, and service continuity. The use case aims to balance seasonality, strengthen regional competitiveness, and promote data-driven decision-making.

The following use case is under development and will be refined based on feedback from upcoming meetings with data consumers/providers. Adjustments may still occur as the work progresses.

Use Case 1: Marketing Assistant – Data-Driven Campaigns for Year-Round Tourism

Needs Addressed. Tourism SMEs in Lapland depend heavily on winter tourism (the high season) and lack data-driven tools to attract visitors year-round. Limited resources and fragmented data make it difficult to identify new segments, evaluate marketing performance, and effectively promote summer and low-season tourism.

The objective is to develop a data-driven application that enables SMEs to plan, test, and evaluate marketing campaigns for year-round tourism, supporting balanced visitor flows and competitiveness.

Functional Description. The solution allows SMEs to identify optimal timing, audiences, and messaging by combining accommodation, activity, flight, and search data. It aims to make data-driven marketing accessible, foster learning from results, and encourage continuous improvement through shared data insights.

Stakeholders.

Document name:	D4.2 First quarterly report on DEPLOYTOUR pilot implementation	Page:	49 of 53
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU
	Version:	0.1	Status: Draft pending approval

This document translates some of the obligations from the grant agreement and in case of discrepancies, it is the grant agreement which prevails over this deliverable.

- **Data Providers:** Visit Levi, Visit Finland/Visit Finland DataHub, local SMEs (activity and accommodation providers), The Data Appeal Company (to be confirmed).
- **Data Consumers:** Tourism SMEs and DMOs applying data to enhance marketing efficiency and promote year-round tourism.

3.5.3 Identification of data sources

Once the use case was defined, the pilot applied a needs-driven process to identify and assess relevant data sources for SME use cases. Existing tourism data ecosystem actors in Lapland and Finland were reviewed to ensure alignment with the European Tourism Data Space framework. Stakeholders, including SMEs, Visit Levi, Travel Tech companies, and other data holders, were invited to specify their “data needs,” which guided expert evaluation of potential datasets.

Key data providers, including Visit Finland, Statistics Finland, Finavia, FMI, Fintraffic, the DMO, and Levi-based companies, were mapped and assessed for data relevance, accessibility, and interoperability. The identified sources include open and semi-open interfaces (e.g. PxWeb APIs, REST, and OGC formats), ensuring technical readiness for future integration.

The pilot is working closely with WP2 and WP3 to align data formats, metadata, and governance models within the common DEPLOYTOUR architecture. Negotiations with data owners are ongoing to define legal and operational conditions for data sharing, ensuring compliance and long-term reusability.

As in other pilots, data providers and consumers themselves negotiate the terms and conditions for data exchange and use. This collaborative process requires time because it ensures the identified datasets are interoperable, accessible, and compliant with both project and regulatory requirements.

Table 27. KPI Total number of data providers identified (Pilot 5)

KPI 2: Total number of DATA PROVIDERS identified	11
• <i>Data providers in the phase: JUST HYPOTHESIS</i>	2
• <i>Data providers in the phase: ONGOING VALIDATION</i>	9
• <i>Data providers in the phase: COMPLETELY VALIDATED</i>	0
• <i>Data providers in the phase: ONBOARDING COMPLETED</i>	0
• <i>Data providers in the phase: DATA SHARING COMPLETED</i>	0

Table 28. KPI Total number of datasets identified (Pilot 5)

KPI 3: Total number of DATASETS identified for sharing	11
• <i>Datasets in the phase: JUST HYPOTHESIS</i>	2
• <i>Datasets in the phase: ONGOING VALIDATION</i>	9
• <i>Datasets in the phase: COMPLETELY VALIDATED</i>	0
• <i>Datasets in the phase: ONBOARDING COMPLETED</i>	0
• <i>Datasets in the phase: DATA SHARING COMPLETED</i>	0

Table 29. KPI Total number of datasets of non-open data identified (Pilot 5)

KPI 4: Total number of DATASETS of NON-OPEN DATA identified for sharing	8
• <i>Datasets in the phase: JUST HYPOTHESIS</i>	2
• <i>Datasets in the phase: ONGOING VALIDATION</i>	6
• <i>Datasets in the phase: COMPLETELY VALIDATED</i>	0
• <i>Datasets in the phase: ONBOARDING COMPLETED</i>	0

Document name:	D4.2 First quarterly report on DEPLOYTOUR pilot implementation	Page:	50 of 53
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU
	Version:	0.1	Status: Draft pending approval

• Datasets in the phase: DATA SHARING COMPLETED	0
---	---

The data sources listed in the table below represent those currently under consideration and active work within the project. At this stage, their status is *ongoing validation*, meaning there are still details that need evaluation from both technical and governance perspectives before confirmation.

Table 30. Data sources identified (Pilot 5)

Data Source	Relative use cases	Usage	Accessibility (open/proprietary)
Accommodation or Activities SMEs (e.g. Levi Suites, Levi Ski Resort)	UC1	Identify traveler profiles Campaign targeting Seasonality analysis	Proprietary: Accommodation or activity SME
DMO Visit Levi	UC1	UC1: Identify traveler profiles Campaign targeting Seasonality analysis	Proprietary: DMO Visit Levi
Visit Finland Datahub	UC1	Audience segmentation Service benchmarking	Proprietary: Visit Finland
Municipality of Kittilä	UC1	UC 1 Event-based campaign planning	Proprietary: Municipality
OpenStreetMap (Overpass API)	UC1	Map-based targeting POI analysis	Open access
Google Trends	UC1	Market interest analysis Campaign timing	Open access
Meta Ad Library	UC1	Competitor benchmarking Campaign design	Open access
YouTube Data API	UC1	Organic content performance	Proprietary: Google/YouTube (publicly accessible under Google's terms of service)
Visit Finland	UC1	Market insights Strategic planning	Proprietary: Visit Finland
Statistics Finland	UC1	Foreign visitor statistics to identify traveller profiles	Proprietary: Statistics Finland. Data can be used freely for any purpose, provided the source is cited.

Document name:	D4.2 First quarterly report on DEPLOYTOUR pilot implementation	Page:	51 of 53
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU
	Version:	0.1	Status: Draft pending approval

This document translates some of the obligations from the grant agreement and in case of discrepancies, it is the grant agreement which prevails over this deliverable.

The Data Appeal Company	UC1	POI data and sentiment, OTA saturation and rates, flight searches and bookings (estimated length of stay, travellers' origins, bookings' type), events data and foreseen impacts (spending and attendance)	Proprietary
-------------------------	-----	--	-------------

3.5.4 Identification and involvement of stakeholders

The stakeholder identification and engagement process for Pilot 5 followed a structured, needs-based, and iterative approach. The objective was to map and engage key actors across Lapland’s tourism ecosystem—from data providers to SME end users—to ensure the pilot reflects real operational needs. Stakeholders were selected based on their roles in the tourism data ecosystem, their data production or use, and their willingness to collaborate within the ETDS. The mapping covered three levels: national (Visit Finland, Statistics Finland, Finavia), regional (Finnish Lapland Tourism Board, University of Lapland, Lapland Regional Council), and destination level (Visit Levi, local SMEs, municipality of Kittilä).

Interviews and meetings in spring 2025 clarified stakeholder needs, capacities, and potential roles.

- March–May 2025: Interviews with SMEs, the DMO, TravelTech and data companies, and the municipality to assess needs and readiness.
- May 2025: Co-creation workshop in Levi refined and prioritised use cases.
- Throughout 2025: One-to-one meetings ensured continuous engagement.
- October 2025: A regional event in Levi reached over 130 companies, expanding participation, raising awareness, and strengthening the data ecosystem.

Visit Levi is a key stakeholder providing destination-level data, coordinating SME engagement, and supporting validation. SMEs act as co-developers and data consumers, testing early concepts and giving feedback. Several Levi-based companies have expressed willingness to share data within the ETDS for the Pilot 5 use case. National stakeholders provide key datasets for marketing planning, while regional actors support communication, onboarding, and scaling results. Both national and regional actors are actively engaged through strategic and operational discussions, and data-sharing negotiations are ongoing. Their involvement is currently consultative and preparatory but progressing toward operational participation. The Data Appeal Company maintains relevant datasets, with availability under discussion, and regional TravelTech actors are positioned to contribute technical expertise and complementary data capabilities to the evolving pilot ecosystem.

Key stakeholders span all levels of Lapland’s tourism data ecosystem and underpin long-term cooperation and scalability.

Document name:	D4.2 First quarterly report on DEPLOYTOUR pilot implementation	Page:	52 of 53
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination: PU	Version: 0.1 Status: Draft pending approval

This document translates some of the obligations from the grant agreement and in case of discrepancies, it is the grant agreement which prevails over this deliverable.

Conclusion

The **technical implementation** phase began a few weeks ago, and preparatory work has laid the foundation for future development in close coordination with WP2. The pilots’ partners are currently defining the conditions for data access, reuse, and governance to ensure interoperability within the European Tourism Data Space (ETDS). Early efforts include identifying exploitable data products and mapping potential users and services that could benefit from them. The exploitation strategy will ensure that data shared through the ETDS generates long-term value, supporting both destination management decisions and the creation of innovative data-based services for tourism stakeholders.

The work carried out has primarily focused on laying the technical, organisational, and semantic groundwork required to support implementation. This includes:

- The identification and structuring of relevant data sources
- The alignment of those sources with ETDS metadata and interoperability standards
- The engagement of stakeholders for data provision, governance, and technical integration
- The identification of detailed use cases and their feasibility assessment

Ongoing refinement of use case DPOs is crucial for assessing data product maturity, defining access mechanisms, and validating data readiness, ensuring all components align with the project’s technical roadmap and governance framework. In parallel, work is underway to define the reference architecture that will guide the data integration process, the stakeholders’ technical roles, and the data governance model to ensure sustainability.

In summary, while implementation has not yet begun, all foundational activities are directly aimed at de-risking and accelerating the upcoming technical phase.

The next quarterly progress reports will also give evidence of:

- Technical implementation progress
- Data exploitation

Document name:	D4.2 First quarterly report on DEPLOYTOUR pilot implementation				Page:	53 of 53
Reference:	D4.2	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	0.1	Status: Draft pending approval

This document translates some of the obligations from the grant agreement and in case of discrepancies, it is the grant agreement which prevails over this deliverable.